

Report of The International Body on Arms Decommissioning

January 24, 1996

I. INTRODUCTION

1. On 28 November, 1995, the British and Irish Governments issued a Communique; which announced the launching in Northern Ireland of a "'twin track' process to make progress in parallel on the decommissioning issue and on all-party negotiations."
2. One track was "to invite the parties to intensive preparatory talks with a remit to reach widespread agreement on the basis, participation, structure, format and agenda to bring all parties together for substantive negotiations aimed at a political settlement based on consent." This has become known as the political track.
3. The other track concerned the decommissioning of arms and was set forth as follows in the Communique:

5. "In parallel, the two Governments have agreed to establish an International Body to provide an independent assessment of the decommissioning issue.

6. "Recognising the widely expressed desire to see all arms removed from Irish politics, the two Governments will ask the International Body to report on the arrangements necessary for the removal from the political equation of arms silenced by virtue of the welcome decisions taken last summer and autumn by those organisations that previously supported the use of arms for political purposes.

7. "In particular, the two Governments will ask the Body to:

identify and advise on a suitable and acceptable method for full and verifiable decommissioning; and

report whether there is a clear commitment on the part of those in possession of such arms to work constructively to achieve that.

8. "It will be for the International Body to determine its own procedures. The two Governments expect it to consult widely, to invite relevant parties to submit their analysis of matters relevant to the decommissioning issue and, in reaching its conclusions within its remit, to consider such evidence on its merits."

4. We are that Body. This is our report. We have no stake in Northern Ireland other than an interest in seeing an end to the conflict and in the ability of its people to live in peace. Our role is to bring an independent perspective to the issue. We are motivated solely by our wish to help. This assessment represents our best and our independent judgment. We are unanimous in our views. There are no differences of opinion among us.

5. To provide us with sufficient information to meet our remit, we held two series of meetings in Belfast, Dublin and London: the first, 15th through 18th December, 1995: the second, 11th through 22nd January, 1996.

In addition, we held an organisational meeting in New York on December 9th, 1995.

6. In the course of our meetings we heard orally and in writing from dozens of government officials, political leaders, church officials and representatives of other organisations and institutions. We received hundreds of letters and telephone calls from members of the public and met with many others.

We thank all for their submissions.

Contributions from those who suffered losses during the time of troubles but are strongly committed to the peace process were especially moving.

All the submissions have been carefully reviewed and considered.

II. DISCUSSION

7. Our examination of the issues and of the facts, and the perspectives brought to us by those who briefed us or who made written representations to us, convince us that while there is no simple solution to the conflict in Northern Ireland, the factors on which a process for peace must be based are already known. We can indicate the way we believe these factors should be addressed so that decommissioning of arms and all-party negotiations can proceed, but only resolute action by the parties themselves will produce progress.
8. That noted, we are aware of the enormous contribution already made by individuals and groups in advancing the process of peace in Northern Ireland to its current stage. The tireless and courageous efforts of Prime Minister John Major and Taoiseach John Bruton (and before him Albert Reynolds) have been essential to the peace process. They have been joined by other political leaders, institutions, organisations and individuals in the promotion of peace.
9. We considered our task in the light of our responsibility to all of the people of Northern Ireland; the need for the people to be reassured that their democratic and moral expectations can be realised; and in the spirit of serious efforts made by the British and Irish Governments to advance the peace process.
10. For nearly a year and a half the guns have been silent in Northern Ireland. The people want that silence to continue. They want lasting peace in a just society in which paramilitary violence plays no part.

That was the dominant theme expressed in the many letters and calls we received from those in the North and South, Unionist and Nationalist, Catholic and Protestant, Loyalist and Republican.

11. Not with standing reprehensible "punishment" killings and beatings, the sustained observance of the ceasefires should not be devalued. It is a significant factor which must be given due weight in assessing the commitment of the paramilitaries to "work constructively to achieve" full and verifiable decommissioning.
12. Since the ceasefires, the political debate has focused largely on the differences that have prevented the commencement of all-party negotiations intended to achieve an agreed political settlement. This circumstance has obscured the widespread agreement that exists -- so widespread that it tends to be taken for granted. In fact, members of both traditions may be less far apart on the resolution of their differences than they believe.
13. No one should underestimate the value of the consensus for peace, and the fact that no significant group is actively seeking to end it.
14. In paragraph five of the Communique we were asked "to provide an independent assessment of the decommissioning issue" It is a serious issue. It is also a symptom of a larger problem: the absence of trust. Common to many of our meetings were arguments, steeped in history, as to why the other side cannot be trusted. As a consequence, even well-intentioned acts are often viewed with suspicion and hostility.
15. But a resolution of the decommissioning issue -- or any other issue -- will not be found if the parties resort to their vast inventories of historical recrimination. Or, as it was put to us several times, what is really needed is the decommissioning of mind-sets in Northern Ireland.
16. We have asked ourselves how those who have suffered during the many years of internal strife can accept the fact that the establishment of a lasting peace will call for reconciliation with those they hold responsible for their loss and pain. Surely the continued suffering and bereavement of individuals and of families

should never be forgotten.

But if the focus remains on the past, the past will become the future, and that is something no one can desire.

17. Everyone with whom we spoke agrees in principle with the need to decommission. There are differences on the timing and context -- indeed, those differences led to the creation of this Body -- but they should not obscure the nearly universal support which exists for the total and verifiable disarmament of all paramilitary organisations. That must continue to be a principal objective.
18. However the issue of decommissioning is resolved, that alone will not lead directly to all-party negotiations. Much work remains on the many issues involved in the political track. The parties should address those issues with urgency.

III. RECOMMENDATIONS: PRINCIPLES OF DEMOCRACY AND NON-VIOLENCE

19. To reach an agreed political settlement and to take the gun out of Irish politics, there must be commitment and adherence to fundamental principles of democracy and non-violence. Participants in all-party negotiations should affirm their commitment to such principles.
20. Accordingly, we recommend that the parties to such negotiations affirm their total and absolute commitment:

a To democratic and exclusively peaceful means of resolving political issues;

b To the total disarmament of all paramilitary organisations;

c To agree that such disarmament must be verifiable to the satisfaction of an independent commission;

d To renounce for themselves, and to oppose any effort by others, to use force, or threaten to use force, to influence the course or the outcome of all-party negotiations;

e To agree to abide by the terms of any agreement reached in all-party negotiations and to resort to democratic and exclusively peaceful methods in trying to alter any aspect of that outcome with which they may disagree; and,

f To urge that "punishment" killings and beatings stop and to take effective steps to prevent such actions.

21. We join the Governments, religious leaders and many others in condemning "punishment" killings and beatings. They contribute to the fear that those who have used violence to pursue political objectives in the past will do so again in the future. Such actions have no place in a lawful society.
22. Those who demand decommissioning prior to all-party negotiations do so out of concern that the paramilitaries will use force, threaten to use force, to influence the negotiations, or to change any aspect of the outcome of negotiations with which they disagree.

Given the history of Northern Ireland, this is not an unreasonable concern. The principles we recommend address those concerns directly.

23. These commitments, when made and honoured, would remove the threat of force before, during and after all-party negotiations. They would focus all concerned on what is ultimately essential if the gun is to be taken out of Irish

politics: an agreed political settlement and the total and verifiable disarmament of all paramilitary organisations. That should encourage the belief that the peace process will truly be an exercise in democracy, not one influenced by the threat of violence.

IV. COMMITMENT TO DECOMMISSIONING

24. The second of the specific questions in paragraph seven of the Communique asks us "to report whether there is a clear commitment on the part of those in possession of such arms to work constructively to achieve" full and verifiable decommissioning.
25. We have concluded that there is a clear commitment on the part of those in possession of such arms to work constructively to achieve full and verifiable decommissioning as part of the process of all-party negotiations; but that commitment does not include decommissioning prior to such negotiations.
26. After careful consideration, on the basis of intensive discussions with the Governments, the political parties, religious leaders, the security forces, and many others, we have concluded that the paramilitary organisations will not decommission any arms prior to all-party negotiations. That was the unanimous and emphatically expressed view of the representatives of the political parties close to paramilitary organisations on both sides. It was also the view of the vast majority of the organisations and individuals who made oral and written submissions. It is not that they are all opposed to prior decommissioning. To the contrary, many favour it. But they are convinced that it will not happen. That is the reality with which all concerned must deal.
27. Competing views were advanced on prior decommissioning. One was that decommissioning of arms must occur prior to all-party negotiations. We were told that the clearest demonstration of adherence to democratic principles, and of a permanent end to the use of violence, is the safe removal and disposal of paramilitary arms, and that at this time only a start to decommissioning will provide the confidence necessary for all-party negotiations to commence. In this view, all parties were aware of the need for prior decommissioning before the ceasefires were announced and should not now be able to avoid that requirement.
28. In the competing view we were told that decommissioning of arms prior to all-party negotiations was not requested before the announcement of the ceasefires, and that had it been, there would have been no ceasefires; that those who entered into ceasefires did so in the belief they would lead immediately to all-party negotiations; and that the request for prior decommissioning, seriously pursued for the first time months after the ceasefires were declared, is merely a tactic to delay or deny such negotiations. In this view, the ceasefires having been maintained for nearly a year and a half, all-party negotiations should begin immediately with no further requirements.
29. We believe that each side of this argument reflects a core of reasonable concern which deserves to be understood and addressed by the other side.
30. Those who insist on prior decommissioning need to be reassured that the commitment to peaceful and democratic means by those formerly supportive of politically motivated violence is genuine and irreversible, and that the threat or use of such violence will not be invoked to influence the process of negotiations or to change any agreed settlement.
31. Those who have been persuaded to abandon violence for the peaceful political path need to be reassured that a meaningful and inclusive process of negotiation is genuinely being offered to address the legitimate concerns of their traditions and the need for new political arrangements with which all can identify.
32. Clearly, new approaches must be explored to overcome this impasse. That is the purpose of the six principles we recommend. They invoke a comprehensive commitment to democracy and non-violence that is intended to reassure all parties to the negotiations.

V. DECOMMISSIONING DURING ALL-PARTY NEGOTIATIONS

33. One side has insisted that some decommissioning of arms must take place before all-party negotiations can begin. The other side has insisted that no decommissioning can take place until the end of the process, after an agreed settlement has been reached. This has resulted in the current impasse.

34. The parties should consider an approach under which some decommissioning would take place during the process of all-party negotiations, rather than before or after as the parties now urge. Such an approach represents a compromise. If the peace process is to move forward, the current impasse must be overcome. While both sides have been adamant in their positions, both have repeatedly expressed the desire to move forward. This approach provides them that opportunity.
35. In addition, it offers the parties an opportunity to use the process of decommissioning to build confidence one step at a time during negotiations. As progress is made on political issues, even modest mutual steps on decommissioning could help create the atmosphere needed for further steps in a progressive pattern of mounting trust and confidence.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS: GUIDELINES ON THE MODALITIES OF DECOMMISSIONING

36. The first of the specific questions in paragraph seven of the Communique asks us "to identify and advise on a suitable and acceptable method for full and verifiable decommissioning."
37. We recommend the following guidelines on the modalities of decommissioning. These recommendations are realistic in light of the nature and scale of the arsenals in question, estimates of which were provided to us by the Governments and their security forces. We believe these estimates to be accurate.
38. Decommissioning should receive a high priority in all-party negotiations. The details of decommissioning, including supporting confidence-building measures, timing and sequencing, have to be determined by the parties themselves.

The decommissioning process should suggest neither victory nor defeat.

39. The ceasefires and the peace process are products not of surrender but rather of a willingness to address differences through political means. This essential fact should be reflected clearly in the modalities of the decommissioning process, which should not require that any party be seen to surrender.

The decommissioning process should take place to the satisfaction of an independent commission.

40. The decommissioning process should take place to the satisfaction of an independent commission acceptable to all parties. The commission would be appointed by the British and Irish Governments on the basis of consultations with the other parties to the negotiating process.
41. The commission should be able to operate independently in both jurisdictions, and should enjoy appropriate legal status and immunity.
42. In addition to having available to it independent sources of legal and technical advice and adequate field resources to receive and audit armaments and to observe and verify the decommissioning process, the commission should be able to call upon the resources and the relevant technical expertise of the British and Irish Armies, when it is appropriate.

The decommissioning process should result in the complete destruction of armaments in a manner that contributes to public safety.

43. The decommissioning process should result in the complete destruction of the armaments. Procedures for destruction would include the cutting up or chipping of small arms and other weapons, the controlled explosion of ammunition and explosives, and other forms of conventional munitions disposal.
44. The decommissioning process could encompass a variety of methods, subject to negotiation, including:
 - the transfer of armaments to the commission or to the designated representatives of either Government, for subsequent destruction;
 - the provision of information to the commission or to designated representatives of either Government, leading to the discovery of

- armaments for subsequent destruction; and,
- the depositing of armaments for collection and subsequent destruction, by the commission or by representatives of either Government.

Parties should also have the option of destroying their weapons themselves.

45. Priority should be accorded throughout to ensuring that armaments are safely handled and stored, and are not misappropriated.

The decommissioning process should be fully verifiable.

46. Whatever the options chosen for the destruction of armaments, including the destruction of weapons by the parties themselves, verification must occur to the satisfaction of the commission.
47. The commission would record information required to monitor the process effectively. The commission should have available to it the relevant data of the Garda Síochána and the Royal Ulster Constabulary. It would report periodically to relevant parties on progress achieved in the decommissioning process.

The decommissioning process should not expose individuals to prosecution.

48. Individuals involved in the decommissioning process should not be prosecuted for the possession of those armaments; amnesties should be established in law in both jurisdictions. Armaments made available for decommissioning, whether directly or indirectly, should be exempt under law from forensic examination, and information obtained as a result of the decommissioning process should be inadmissible as evidence in courts of law in either jurisdiction.
49. Groups in possession of illegal armaments should be free to organise their participation in the decommissioning process as they judge appropriate, e.g. groups may designate particular individuals to deposit armaments on their behalf.

The decommissioning process should be mutual.

50. Decommissioning would take place on the basis of the mutual commitment and participation of the paramilitary organisations.

This offers the parties another opportunity to use the process of decommissioning to build confidence one step at a time during negotiations.

VII. FURTHER CONFIDENCE-BUILDING

51. It is important for all participants to take steps to build confidence throughout the peace process. In the course of our discussions, many urged that certain actions other than decommissioning be taken to build confidence. We make no recommendations on them since they are outside our remit, but we believe it appropriate to comment on some since success in the peace process cannot be achieved solely by reference to the decommissioning of arms.
52. Support for the use of violence is incompatible with participation in the democratic process. The early termination of paramilitary activities, including surveillance and targeting, would demonstrate a commitment to peaceful methods and so build trust among other parties and alleviate the fears and anxieties of the general population. So, too, would the provision of information on the status of missing persons, and the return of those who have been forced to leave their communities under threat.
53. Continued action by the Governments on prisoners would bolster trust. So would early implementation of the proposed review of emergency legislation, consistent with the evolving security situation.
54. Different views were expressed as to the weapons to be decommissioned. In the Communique, the Governments made clear their view that our remit is limited to those weapons held by paramilitary organisations. We accept and share that view. There is no equivalence between such weapons and those held by security

forces. However, in the context of building mutual confidence, we welcome the commitment of the Governments, as stated in paragraph nine of the Communique, "to continue to take responsive measures, advised by their respective security authorities, as the threat reduces".

55. We share the hope, expressed by many on all sides, that policing in Northern Ireland can be normalised as soon as the security situation permits. A review of the situation with respect to legally registered weapons and the use of plastic bullets, and continued progress toward more balanced representation in the police force would contribute to the building of trust.
56. Several oral and written submissions raised the idea of an elected body. We note the reference in paragraph three of the Communique; to "whether and how an elected body could play a part". Elections held in accordance with democratic principles express and reflect the popular will. If it were broadly acceptable, with an appropriate mandate, and within the three-strand structure, an elective process could contribute to the building of confidence.
57. Finally, the importance of further progress in the social and economic development of Northern Ireland and its communities was emphasised time and again in our meetings, in the context of building confidence and establishing a lasting peace.

VIII. CONCLUDING REMARKS

58. Last week we stood in Belfast and looked at a thirty foot high wall and at barriers topped with iron and barbed wire. The wall, which has ironically come to be known as the "peace line", is a tangible symbol of the division of the people of Northern Ireland into two hostile communities. To the outsider both are warm and generous. Between themselves they are fearful and antagonistic.
59. Yet, it is now clear beyond doubt that the vast majority of the people of both traditions want to turn away from the bitter past. There is a powerful desire for peace in Northern Ireland. It is that desire which creates the present opportunity.
60. This is a critical time in the history of Northern Ireland. The peace process will move forward or this society could slip back to the horror of the past quarter century.
61. Rigid adherence by the parties to their past positions will simply continue the stalemate which has already lasted too long. In a society as deeply divided as Northern Ireland, reaching across the "peace line" requires a willingness to take risks for peace.
62. The risk may seem high but the reward is great: a future of peace, equality and prosperity for all the people of Northern Ireland.

George J. Mitchell; John de Chastelain; Harri Holkeri.

January 22nd, 1996

Northern Ireland Arms Decommissioning Act 1997

CHAPTER 7

ARRANGEMENT OF SECTIONS

Section

1. Decommissioning scheme.
2. Duration of decommissioning scheme.
3. Methods of decommissioning.
4. Amnesty.
5. Evidence.
6. Testing decommissioned articles.
7. The Commission.
8. Arms in England and Wales and Scotland.
9. Expenses.
10. Interpretation.
11. Short title and saving.

SCHEDULE:

—Offences covered by the amnesty.

Northern Ireland Arms Decommissioning Act 1997

1997 CHAPTER 7

An Act to make provision connected with Northern Ireland about the decommissioning of firearms, ammunition and explosives; and for connected purposes. [27th February 1997]

BE IT ENACTED, by the Queen's most Excellent Majesty, by and with the advice and consent of the Lords Spiritual and Temporal, and Commons, in this present Parliament assembled, and by the authority of the same, as follows:-

Decommissioning
scheme.

- 1.**-(1) In this Act a "decommissioning scheme" is any scheme which-
- (a) is made by the Secretary of State to facilitate the decommissioning of firearms, ammunition and explosives in Northern Ireland, and
 - (b) includes provisions satisfying the requirements of sections 2 and 3 (whether or not it also includes other provisions).

1868 c. 37.

(2) Section 2 of the Documentary Evidence Act 1868 (mode of proving certain documents) shall apply to a decommissioning scheme.

Duration of
decommissioning
scheme.

2.-(1) A decommissioning scheme must identify a period during which firearms, ammunition and explosives may be dealt with in accordance with the scheme ("the amnesty period").

(2) The amnesty period must end before-

(a) [27th February 2003¹], or

(b) such later day as the Secretary of State may by order from time to time appoint.

(3) A day appointed by an order under subsection (2)(b) must not be-

(a) more than twelve months after the day on which the order is made,
or

(b) [later than 27th February 2007²].

(4) An order under subsection (2)(b) shall be made by statutory instrument; and no order shall be made unless a draft has been laid before, and approved by resolution of, each House of Parliament.

Methods of
decommissioning.

3.-(1) A decommissioning scheme must make provision for one or more of the following ways of dealing with firearms, ammunition and explosives (and may make provision for others)-

(a) transfer to the Commission mentioned in section 7, or to a designated person, for destruction;

(b) depositing for collection and destruction by the Commission or a designated person;

- (c) provision of information for the purpose of collection and destruction by the Commission or a designated person;
- (d) destruction by persons in unlawful possession.

(2) In subsection (1) "designated person" means a person designated by the Secretary of State or, in the case of firearms, ammunition or explosives transferred or collected in the Republic of Ireland, a person designated by the Minister for Justice of the Republic.

4.-(1) No proceedings shall be brought for an offence listed in the Schedule to this Act in respect of anything done in accordance with a decommissioning scheme.

Amnesty.

(2) The Secretary of State may by order add any offence or description of offence to, or remove any offence or description of offence from, the list in the Schedule to this Act.

(3) An order under subsection (2)-

- (a) shall be made by statutory instrument, and
- (b) may include such transitional provisions as appear to the Secretary of State to be expedient.

(4) No order shall be made under subsection (2) unless a draft has been laid before, and approved by resolution of, each House of Parliament.

5.-(1) A decommissioned article, or information derived from it, shall not be admissible in evidence in criminal proceedings.

Evidence.

(2) Evidence of anything done, and of any information obtained, in accordance with a decommissioning scheme shall not be admissible in criminal proceedings.

(3) Subsections (1) and (2) shall not apply to the admission of evidence adduced in criminal proceedings on behalf of the accused.

(4) Subsection (1) shall not apply to proceedings for an offence alleged to have been committed by the use of, or in relation to, something which was a decommissioned article at the time when the offence is alleged to have been committed.

6.-(1) A person who has received a decommissioned article shall not carry out, or cause or permit anyone else to carry out, a test or procedure in relation to the article the purpose of which is-

Testing decommissioned articles.

- (a) to discover information about anything done with or in relation to any decommissioned article,
- (b) to discover who has been in contact with, or near to, any decommissioned article,
- (c) to discover where any decommissioned article was at any time (including the conditions under which it was kept),
- (d) to discover when any decommissioned article was in contact with, or near to, a particular person or when it was in a particular place or kept under particular conditions,
- (e) to discover when or where any decommissioned article was made, or
- (f) to discover the composition of any decommissioned article.

(2) Subsection (1)(f) does not prohibit a test or procedure the purpose of which is-

- (a) to determine whether an article is, or contains, an explosive or ammunition,
- (b) to determine the quantity of explosive or ammunition present, or
- (c) to determine whether an article can safely be moved or otherwise dealt with.

(3) Subsection (1) does not prohibit a test or procedure the purpose of which is to discover information in relation to a decommissioned article where the information-

- (a) is sought for the purposes of the investigation of an offence alleged to have been committed at a time after the article became a decommissioned article, and
- (b) does not concern the treatment of the article in accordance with a decommissioning scheme.

The Commission.

7.-(1) In this section "the Commission" means an independent organisation established by an agreement, made in connection with the affairs of Northern Ireland between Her Majesty's Government in the United Kingdom and the Government of the Republic of Ireland, to facilitate the decommissioning of firearms, ammunition and explosives.

(2) The Secretary of State may by order-

- (a) confer on the Commission the legal capacities of a body corporate;
- (b) confer on the Commission, in such cases, to such extent and with such modifications as the order may specify, any of the privileges and immunities set out in Part I of Schedule 1 to the International Organisations Act 1968;
- (c) confer on members and servants of the Commission and members of their families who form part of their households, in such cases, to such extent and with such modifications as the order may specify any of the privileges and immunities set out in Parts II, III and V of that Schedule;

(d) make provision about the waiver of privileges and immunities.

In this subsection "servants of the Commission" includes agents of, and persons carrying out work for or giving advice to, the Commission.

(3) An order under subsection (2)-

- (a) may make different provision for different cases (including different provision for different persons);
- (b) shall be made by statutory instrument which shall be subject to annulment in pursuance of a resolution of either House of Parliament.

(4) The Secretary of State may-

- (a) make payments to the Commission or to members of the Commission;
- (b) provide for the Commission such premises and facilities, and the services of such staff, as he thinks appropriate.

(5) This section shall come into force on such day as the Secretary of State, after consulting the Minister for Justice of the Republic of Ireland, may by order made by statutory instrument appoint.

(6) This section shall cease to have effect at the end of such day as the Secretary of State, after consulting the Minister for Justice of the Republic of Ireland, may by order made by statutory instrument appoint; and an

order under this subsection may include such transitional provisions as appear to the Secretary of State to be expedient.

8.-(1) This section applies to any scheme which-

(a) is made by the Secretary of State, for purposes relating to the affairs of Northern Ireland, to facilitate the decommissioning of firearms, ammunition and explosives in England and Wales or in Scotland, and

(b) includes provisions satisfying the requirements of sections 2 and 3 (whether or not it also includes other provisions).

(2) The Secretary of State may by order provide that a scheme to which this section applies shall be a decommissioning scheme for the purposes of this Act.

(3) In relation to a scheme which is a decommissioning scheme by virtue of subsection (2), the Schedule to this Act shall have effect with the substitution for any offence under the law of Northern Ireland of such similar offence under the law of England and Wales, or as the case may be of Scotland, as the Secretary of State may specify by order.

(4) An order under this section shall be made by statutory instrument; and no order shall be made unless a draft has been laid before, and approved by resolution of, each House of Parliament.

9. Any expenses incurred by the Secretary of State in connection with a decommissioning scheme or under section 7(4) shall be paid out of money provided by Parliament.

10.-(1) In this Act-

"ammunition" means anything which is-

(a) ammunition within the meaning of the Firearms (Northern Ireland) Order 1981, or

(b) a component of such ammunition;

"decommissioned article" means-

(a) anything which has been transferred, deposited or collected in accordance with a decommissioning scheme,

(b) anything found on or in, or received with, something falling within paragraph (a), and

(c) a part of, or thing derived from, something falling within paragraph (a) or (b);

"destruction" includes making permanently inaccessible or permanently unusable;

"firearm" means anything which-

(a) is a firearm within the meaning of the Firearms (Northern Ireland) Order 1981,

(b) is an accessory to such a firearm,

(c) is a weapon designed or adapted for the discharge of any thing, or

(d) has the appearance of being one of the things described in paragraphs (a) to (c);

"explosive" means anything which is-

(a) an explosive within the meaning of the Explosives Act 1875, or

Arms in England and
Wales and Scotland

Expenses.

Interpretation.

S.I. 1981/155
(N.I. 2).

S.I. 1981/155
(N.I. 2).

1883 c. 3.

(b) an explosive substance within the meaning of the Explosive Substances Act 1883.

(2) In this Act, references to things done in accordance with a decommissioning scheme include references to things done in accordance with arrangements provided for by a scheme.

Short title and saving.

11.-(1) This Act may be cited as the Northern Ireland Arms Decommissioning Act 1997.

(2) Nothing in this Act shall prejudice any power or discretion exercisable apart from this Act in relation to the institution or conduct of criminal proceedings.

SCHEDULE

Section 4(1).

OFFENCES COVERED BY THE AMNESTY

Explosives Act 1875

1. An offence of contravening any provision of the Explosives Act 1875 or any instrument under that Act.

1875 c. 17.

Explosive Substances Act 1883

2. An offence under section 4 of the Explosive Substances Act 1883 (possession of explosive under suspicious circumstances, &c.).

1883 c. 3.

Criminal Law Act (Northern Ireland) 1967

3. An offence under section 5 of the Criminal Law Act (Northern Ireland) 1967 (concealing offences, &c.).

1967 c. 18 (N.I.).

Theft Act (Northern Ireland) 1969

4. An offence under section 1 or 21 of the Theft Act (Northern Ireland) 1969 (theft and handling stolen goods).

1969 c. 16 (N.I.).

Explosives Act (Northern Ireland) 1970

5. An offence under any provision of the Explosives Act (Northern Ireland) 1970.

1970 c. 10 (N.I.).

Health and Safety at Work (Northern Ireland) Order 1978

6. An offence under any provision of the Health and Safety at Work (Northern Ireland) Order 1978.

S.I. 1978/1039
(N.I. 9).

Customs and Excise Acts 1979

7. An offence under any provision of the Customs and Excise Acts 1979 (within the meaning of the Customs and Excise Management Act 1979).

1979 c. 2.

Firearms (Northern Ireland) Order 1981

8. An offence under any of the following provisions of the Firearms (Northern Ireland) Order 1981:

S.I. 1981/155
(N.I. 2).

- (a) article 3(1) (possession, &c. of firearm or ammunition not authorised by firearm certificate);
- (b) article 4(1) and (2) (transactions with firearms and ammunition);
- (c) article 6(1), (1A) and (4) (prohibited firearms and ammunition);
- (d) article 7 (movement of firearms and ammunition);
- (e) article 18(2), in so far as it concerns possession of firearms or imitation firearms at the time of being arrested;
- (f) article 20(1) (carrying firearms in a public place);
- (g) article 21 (trespassing with firearms);
- (h) article 22(5) and (7) (possession of firearms by person previously convicted of crime, &c.);
- (i) article 23 (possession of firearms and ammunition in suspicious circumstances);

- (j) article 26 (acquisition and possession of firearms and ammunition by persons under 18);
- (k) article 43 (failure to comply with requirements relating to transactions in firearms, &c.).

Prevention of Terrorism (Temporary Provisions) Act 1989

- 1989 c. 4. 9. An offence under either of the following provisions of the Prevention of Terrorism (Temporary Provisions) Act 1989-
- (a) section 10(1)(b) (making property available for the benefit of a proscribed organisation, &c.);
 - (b) section 18 (failure to disclose information about acts of terrorism).

Northern Ireland (Emergency Provisions) Act 1996

- 1996 c. 22. 10. An offence under any of the following provisions of the Northern Ireland (Emergency Provisions) Act 1996-
- (a) section 29 (directing terrorist organisation);
 - (b) section 30(1)(c) (inviting persons to carry out orders on behalf of a proscribed organisation, &c.);
 - (c) section 30(1)(d)(ii) or (iii) (meetings);
 - (d) section 31 (display of support in public for proscribed organisation);
 - (e) section 32 (possession of items intended for terrorist purposes);
 - (f) section 35 (wearing of hoods, &c. in public place).

Inchoate offences

11. The offence of aiding, abetting, counselling, procuring or inciting the commission of an offence specified in this Schedule.

12. The offence of attempting or conspiring to commit an offence specified in this Schedule.

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- 1. Subst., 2002 c. 6 s. 1(2)
 - 2. Subst., 2002 c. 6 s. 1(3)

Number 3 of 1997

DECOMMISSIONING ACT, 1997

ARRANGEMENT OF SECTIONS

Section

1. Interpretation.
 2. Regulations in relation to decommissioning.
 3. Provisions relating to Commission.
 4. Regulations in relation to Commission.
 5. Prohibition of certain proceedings.
 6. Prohibition of certain testing, etc., and certain evidence.
 7. General provisions as to regulations.
 8. Expenses.
 9. Short title and commencement.
-

[No. 3.] *Decommissioning Act, 1997.* [1997.]

ACTS REFERRED TO

Explosive Substances Act, 1883	1883, c. 3
Explosives Act, 1875	1875, c. 17
Firearms Act, 1925	1925, No. 17
Firearms Acts, 1925 to 1990	

Number 3 of 1997

DECOMMISSIONING ACT, 1997

AN ACT TO MAKE PROVISION IN RELATION TO THE DECOMMISSIONING OF FIREARMS, AMMUNITION AND EXPLOSIVES AND FOR THAT PURPOSE TO MAKE PROVISION IN RELATION TO A COMMISSION ESTABLISHED BY AGREEMENT BETWEEN THE GOVERNMENT AND THE GOVERNMENT OF THE UNITED KINGDOM AND TO PROVIDE FOR RELATED MATTERS. [26th February, 1997]

BE IT ENACTED BY THE OIREACHTAS AS FOLLOWS:

1.—(1) In this Act, save where the context otherwise requires— Interpretation.

“act” includes omission and a reference to the doing of an act includes a reference to the making of an omission;

“the agreement” means the agreement between the Government and the Government of the United Kingdom establishing the Commission;

“arms” means a firearm within the meaning of the Firearms Acts, 1925 to 1990, and includes ammunition within the meaning of the Firearms Act, 1925, an explosive within the meaning of the Explosives Act, 1875, and any other substance or thing that is an explosive substance within the meaning of the Explosive Substances Act, 1883;

“arrangements” means arrangements made by the Commission pursuant to regulations;

“the Commission” means the commission established by the agreement;

“the corresponding law” means the law of the United Kingdom corresponding to this Act;

“decommissioning”, in relation to arms, means—

- (a) destroying the arms, or
- (b) transferring to, or doing an act leading to the collection and destruction of the arms by or on behalf of, the Commission or a person designated by the Minister or, if appropriate, the Secretary of State, in or outside the State, and cognate words shall be construed accordingly;

[No. 3.] *Decommissioning Act, 1997.* [1997.]

- S.1 “destruction” includes making permanently inaccessible or unusable and cognate words shall be construed accordingly;
- “enactment” includes an instrument made under a power conferred by statute;
- “functions” includes powers and duties;
- “the Minister” means the Minister for Justice;
- “regulations” means regulations made by the Minister under this Act;
- “Secretary of State” means a Secretary of State in the Government of the United Kingdom.

(2) In this Act—

- (a) a reference to a section is a reference to a section of this Act, unless it is indicated that reference to some other provision is intended, and
- (b) a reference to a paragraph or subparagraph is a reference to a paragraph or subparagraph of the provision in which the reference occurs, unless it is indicated that reference to some other provision is intended, and
- (c) a reference to any enactment shall be construed as a reference to that enactment as amended, adapted or extended by or under any subsequent enactment.

Regulations in relation to decommissioning.

2.—(1) Regulations may provide for the decommissioning of arms.

(2) Without prejudice to the generality of *subsection (1)*, regulations may make provision in relation to—

- (a) the locations at which, the procedures by which and the times at or during which the decommissioning of arms or any particular method or manner of such decommissioning may take place,
- (b) the methods and manners by and in which the decommissioning of arms may take place including—
 - (i) the transfer of arms to the Commission or to a person designated by the Minister or (if the transfer is to a person outside the State in accordance with the corresponding law) the Secretary of State for destruction,
 - (ii) the provision of information to the Commission or to a person in the State designated by the Minister or (if the information is provided to a person outside the State in accordance with the corresponding law) a person designated by the Secretary of State leading to the collection and destruction of arms by the Commission or a person designated by the Minister or (in the case of arms outside the State) the Secretary of State,
 - (iii) the depositing of arms for collection and destruction by the Commission or a person designated by the

[1997.] *Decommissioning Act, 1997.* [No. 3.]

Minister or (in the case of arms deposited outside S.2
the State in accordance with the corresponding law)
the Secretary of State,

(iv) the destruction of arms by those in possession of
them,

and

(c) the destruction of arms decommissioned in accordance with
subparagraph (i), (ii) or (iii) of paragraph (b).

3.—(1) The subsequent provisions of this section shall come into operation on such day as the Minister, after consultation with the Secretary of State, may, for the purpose of enabling the agreement to have full effect, by order appoint. Provisions relating to Commission.

(2) The Commission shall be independent in the performance of its functions.

(3) The Commission shall have the legal capacity of a body corporate.

(4) (a) The Minister may by order make provision for the purposes of *paragraph (b)* as respects inviolability, exemptions, facilities and immunities, privileges and rights in relation to the Commission.

(b) The Commission, its property and a person (being a member of the Commission or a member of the staff of, or a person performing functions assigned to him or her by, the Commission, an agent of the Commission or a member of the person's family who forms part of his or her household) shall have and enjoy inviolability, exemptions, facilities and immunities, privileges and rights in such manner, to such extent and subject to such limitations (including the waiver thereof) as may be provided for in each case in the order under *paragraph (a)*.

(c) An order made under this section may make different provision for different cases or classes of case.

(5) The Minister may by order amend or revoke an order under this section (other than *subsection (1)*).

(6) The Commission shall stand dissolved upon such day as the Minister may, after consultation with the Secretary of State, by order appoint, and the Minister may include in the order such transitional or consequential provisions as appear to him or her to be expedient.

(7) An order under this section shall be laid before each House of the Oireachtas as soon as may be after it is made and, if a resolution annulling the order is passed by either such House within the next 21 days on which that House has sat after the order has been laid before it, the order shall be annulled accordingly, but without prejudice to the validity of anything previously done thereunder.

4.—(1) Regulations may make provision in relation to the Commission. Regulations in relation to Commission.

(2) Without prejudice to the generality of *subsection (1)*, regulations may provide for—

- (a) the membership of the Commission, including the number of members thereof,
- (b) the terms and conditions upon and subject to which the members of the Commission shall hold office as such members and the terms and conditions of employment of any staff of the Commission,
- (c) the provision to the Commission of such moneys, premises, facilities and services (including the services of staff) as may be necessary for the performance of its functions,
- (d) the maintenance by the Commission, and the inspection by or on behalf of the Minister and the Secretary of State, of accounts of moneys received or expended by the Commission,
- (e) the proof of documents executed on behalf of the Commission,
- (f) the prohibition of the disclosure by a member of the Commission or of the staff of the Commission or by any person providing a service to the Commission of information obtained by such member or person in the course of the performance of his or her functions as such member or person unless such disclosure is authorised by or on behalf of the Commission,
- (g) the functions of the Commission and its role generally in relation to the decommissioning of arms or any particular method or manner of such decommissioning, which functions may include all or any one or more of the following:
 - (i) the making of arrangements for the decommissioning of arms and the joining or assisting by the Commission in the carrying out of any such arrangements,
 - (ii) the taking possession of arms decommissioned pursuant to regulations or arrangements,
 - (iii) the observation and verification and, where appropriate, the supervision of the decommissioning of arms taking place in accordance with regulations or arrangements,
 - (iv) the recording of such information as may be specified for the purpose of monitoring the process of the decommissioning of arms,
 - (v) the making of reports on specified matters to such persons as may be specified,
 - (vi) the facilitating of the safe and secure movement, handling and storage of arms during and after their decommissioning, and the supervision of such movement, handling and storage,

- (h) any other matters that the Minister considers necessary for the purposes of this Act.

5.—(1) Proceedings shall not be instituted against a person for an offence in relation to any particular arms if— Prohibition of certain proceedings.

- (a) at the time of its commission, the person was engaged in the process of the decommissioning of those arms in accordance with regulations or arrangements,
- (b) the requirements of the regulations or arrangements were satisfied as respects the person and the decommissioning,
- (c) the decommissioning was taking or took place at a time or during a period standing specified in the regulations, and
- (d) the act constituting the offence or an act that is an ingredient of the offence was a part of the process of the decommissioning and was done in pursuance of the regulations or arrangements.

(2) Without prejudice to the generality of *subsection (1)*, regulations may specify offences to which it applies.

(3) Regulations may provide that *subsection (1)*, in so far as it relates to any particular method or manner of decommissioning of arms, shall apply only to specified offences.

(4) Where arms have been decommissioned in accordance with regulations or arrangements, *subsection (1)* shall not apply to proceedings for an offence alleged to have been committed, after the decommissioning, by the use of, or in relation to, those arms.

6.—(1) Subject to *subsections (2) and (3)*— Prohibition of certain testing, etc., and certain evidence.

- (a) arms being made available for the purposes of decommissioning in accordance with regulations or arrangements or taken into the possession of the Commission or a person designated by the Minister for the purposes of or following such decommissioning,
- (b) anything resulting from the process of the decommissioning of arms in accordance with regulations or arrangements,
- (c) any substance or thing found on or in any arms decommissioned in accordance with regulations or arrangements, or
- (d) anything on or in which arms decommissioned in accordance with regulations or arrangements were when so decommissioned or any substance or other thing found on or in such a thing,

shall not be subjected to forensic examination or to testing.

(2) *Subsection (1)* does not apply to a forensic examination or to testing of—

[No. 3.] *Decommissioning Act, 1997.* [1997.]

S.6

- (a) any substance or thing decommissioned in accordance with regulations or arrangements,
- (b) any substance or thing referred to in *paragraph (b), (c) or (d) of subsection (1)*,

for the purpose of—

- (i) determining—
 - (I) if it is or contains ammunition or an explosive or explosive substance,
 - (II) the quantity of ammunition, explosives or explosive substances present, or
 - (III) if the condition of the substance or thing is safe and stable,
- or
- (ii) discovering information concerning an offence alleged to have been committed after the decommissioning concerned.

(3) Arms decommissioned in accordance with regulations or arrangements or any other substance or thing referred to in *subsection (1)* or information obtained in the course, or as a result, of the decommissioning of arms in accordance with regulations or arrangements shall not be admissible in evidence by or on behalf of the State in proceedings in any court for an offence (other than an offence referred to in *subsection (2)(ii)*) or in any appeal in relation to any such proceedings.

(4) Evidence of anything done for the purposes of the decommissioning of arms in accordance with regulations or arrangements shall not be admissible by or on behalf of the State in proceedings in any court for an offence (other than an offence referred to in *subsection (2)(ii)*) or in any appeal in relation to such proceedings.

(5) (a) In this section, save where the context otherwise requires—

“ammunition” has the meaning assigned to it by the Firearms Act, 1925;

“explosive” means an explosive within the meaning of the Explosives Act, 1875;

“explosive substance” has the meaning assigned to it by the Explosive Substances Act, 1883;

“firearm” has the meaning assigned to it by the Firearms Acts, 1925 to 1990.

(b) In this section references to arms or firearms or ammunition or an explosive or explosive substance include references to any substance or thing that is a firearm or ammunition or an explosive or explosive substance for the purpose of the corresponding law and references to decommissioning and decommissioned shall be construed accordingly.

[1997.] *Decommissioning Act, 1997.* [No. 3.]

7.—(1) The Minister may make regulations for any purpose in relation to which regulations are provided for by any of the provisions of this Act. General provisions as to regulations.

(2) Regulations under this section shall be laid before each House of the Oireachtas as soon as may be after they are made and, if a resolution annulling the regulations is passed by either such House within the next 21 days on which that House has sat after the regulations have been laid before it, the regulations shall be annulled accordingly, but without prejudice to the validity of anything previously done thereunder.

(3) Without prejudice to any specific provision of this Act, any regulations may contain such incidental or supplementary provisions as may appear to the Minister to be expedient for the purposes of the regulations.

8.—The expenses incurred by the Minister in the administration of this Act shall, to such extent as may be sanctioned by the Minister for Finance, be paid out of moneys provided by the Oireachtas. Expenses.

9.—(1) This Act may be cited as the Decommissioning Act, 1997. Short title and commencement.

(2) This Act (other than *section 3*) shall come into operation on such day or days as, by order or orders made by the Minister under this section, may be fixed therefor either generally or with reference to any particular purpose or provision and different days may be so fixed for different purposes and different provisions.

Treaty Series No. 54 (1997)

Agreement

between the Government of the
United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland
and the Government of the Republic of Ireland

Establishing the Independent International Commission on Decommissioning

Belfast, 26 August 1997

[The Agreement entered into force, upon the exchange of
notifications of acceptance, on 24 September 1997]

*Presented to Parliament
by the Secretary of State for Foreign and Commonwealth Affairs
by Command of Her Majesty*

1997

**AGREEMENT BETWEEN THE GOVERNMENT OF
THE UNITED KINGDOM OF GREAT BRITAIN AND NORTHERN IRELAND
AND THE GOVERNMENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF IRELAND
ESTABLISHING THE INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION
ON DECOMMISSIONING**

The Government of the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland and the Government of the Republic of Ireland:

Recalling their decision on the 28th day of November 1995 to establish an International Body to provide an independent assessment of the decommissioning issue;

Noting that the Report of the International Body presented to the two Governments on the 22nd day of January 1996 recommended that the decommissioning process should take place to the satisfaction of an independent commission;

Noting that the Decommissioning Act, 1997 in the Republic of Ireland and the Northern Ireland Arms Decommissioning Act 1997 in the United Kingdom make reference to a Commission to be established by agreement between the two Governments;

Recalling the Joint Communiqué issued on the 29th July 1997, following the meeting between the Minister for Foreign Affairs and the Secretary of State for Northern Ireland, in which they announced their decision to complete preparations for the establishment of an Independent Commission in order that the mechanisms on decommissioning would be capable of being launched simultaneously with substantive political negotiations;

Have agreed as follows:

ARTICLE 1

The Independent International Commission on Decommissioning (hereinafter referred to as “the Commission”) is hereby established by the two Governments in accordance with this Agreement.

ARTICLE 2

(1) The Commission shall be independent in the performance of its functions.

(2) The Commission shall have the legal capacity of a body corporate in accordance with the Decommissioning Act, 1997 and any Order made by the Secretary of State under the Northern Ireland Arms Decommissioning Act 1997.

ARTICLE 3

The objective of the Commission is to facilitate the decommissioning of firearms, ammunition, explosives and explosive substances (hereinafter referred to as “arms”) in accordance with the Report of the International Body, any regulations or arrangements made under the Decommissioning Act, 1997 and any decommissioning schemes within the meaning of section 1 of the Northern Ireland Arms Decommissioning Act 1997.

ARTICLE 4

In fulfilment of the objective set out in Article 3, the Commission shall have the following functions:

- (a) to consult with the participants in political negotiations in Northern Ireland, including both Governments, and others whom it deems relevant on the type of scheme or schemes for decommissioning including the role it might play in respect of each scheme;
- (b) to present to the two Governments proposals for schemes for decommissioning having due regard to the views expressed by those it has consulted;
- (c) to undertake, in accordance with any regulations or arrangements made under the Decommissioning Act, 1997 and any decommissioning schemes within the meaning of section 1, and in accordance with section 3, of the Northern Ireland Arms Decommissioning Act 1997, such tasks that may be required of it to facilitate the decommissioning of arms, including observing, monitoring and verifying decommissioning and receiving and auditing arms; and
- (d) to report periodically to both Governments and, through whatever mechanisms they may establish for that purpose, the other participants in political negotiations in Northern Ireland.

ARTICLE 5

The Commission shall consist of not less than two members. The members shall be appointed jointly by the two Governments who may also appoint additional members from time to time. The two Governments may jointly appoint one of the members as Chairperson. The members of the Commission shall serve on terms and conditions decided by the two Governments.

ARTICLE 6

The Commission, its property and premises, and the persons referred to in section 3(4)(b) of the Decommissioning Act, 1997 and in section 7(2)(c) of the Northern Ireland Arms Decommissioning Act 1997 shall have such privileges, immunities and inviolabilities as may be conferred or provided for in accordance with orders made by the Minister for Justice, Equality and Law Reform and the Secretary of State under those Acts.

ARTICLE 7

Such moneys, premises, facilities and services as may be necessary for the proper functioning of the Commission shall be provided by the two Governments on a basis to be determined by them.

ARTICLE 8

Members of the Commission, members of the staff of the Commission, persons carrying out work for or giving advice to the Commission and agents of the Commission shall be bound not to disclose any information obtained in the course of the performance of their functions as such members or persons unless such disclosure is authorised by or on behalf of the Commission.

ARTICLE 9

The Commission shall keep proper accounts and proper records of all moneys received or expended by it and shall, at the joint request of the two Governments, appoint auditors who shall audit the accounts of the Commission. The reports of the auditors shall be submitted to both Governments.

ARTICLE 10

The Minister for Justice, Equality and Law Reform and the Secretary of State may make further provision in relation to the Commission and the decommissioning of arms in accordance with the Decommissioning Act, 1997 and any decommissioning schemes within the meaning of section 1 of the Northern Ireland Arms Decommissioning Act 1997.

ARTICLE 11

This Agreement shall enter into force on the date on which the two Governments exchange notifications of their acceptance of it.

ARTICLE 12

The Agreement shall continue in force until terminated by mutual agreement and thereafter shall cease to have effect save in so far as and to the extent necessary for meeting any liabilities or disposing in an orderly manner of any remaining assets of the Commission in accordance with the spirit of the Agreement.

In witness whereof the undersigned, being duly authorised thereto by their respective Governments, have signed this Agreement.

Done at Belfast in two originals on the 26th day of August 1997.

For the Government of the United Kingdom
of Great Britain and Northern Ireland:

For the Government of the Republic of Ireland:

MARJORIE MOWLAM

RAY BURKE

The Agreement entered into force on 24 September 1997

**Decommissioning Scheme
based on Section 3(1)(c)
and (d) of the
Northern Ireland
Arms Decommissioning
Act 1997**

Introduction

1. This is a decommissioning scheme within the meaning of section 1 of the Northern Ireland Arms Decommissioning Act 1997 (“the 1997 Act”), made by the Secretary of State to facilitate the decommissioning of firearms, ammunition and explosives (“arms”) in Northern Ireland. It comes into force on 30 June 1998 and, accordingly, a person can start to act in accordance with the scheme from that date.
2. It makes provision for the decommissioning of arms by one or a combination of the following methods in section 3(1)(c) and (d) of the 1997 Act: the provision of information for the purpose of collection and destruction by the Commission; and destruction by persons in unlawful possession.
3. Words and phrases used in this scheme bear the same meaning as in the 1997 Act save where the contrary is expressly stated.
4. In this scheme,
 - (i) “the Commission” means the Independent International Commission established by agreement between the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland and the Republic of Ireland made on 26th August 1997 and, as regards the functions of the Commission in paragraphs 16, 17, 21, 22 and 23 of this scheme, includes any person duly authorised by the Commission to perform on its behalf the functions of the Commission;
 - (ii) “proscribed organisation” means an organisation specified in Schedule 2 to the Northern Ireland (Emergency Provisions) Act 1996; and
 - (iii) “contact person” means a person who has given notice to the Commission in accordance with paragraph 7.

5. For the purposes of section 2(1) of the 1997 Act, the period during which arms may be dealt with in accordance with the scheme (“the amnesty period”) begins on 30 June 1998 and ends on [24 February 2005]¹.

Provision of information by the Commission

6. The Commission may provide a person who seeks information in relation to the decommissioning of arms and the application of this scheme with such information as it considers appropriate.

Notice of intention to decommission arms

7. A person who proposes to decommission arms on behalf of a proscribed organisation in accordance with this scheme shall, before doing any other act leading to decommissioning, give notice to the Commission of the proposal, in accordance with arrangements decided by the Commission.

A person starts to act in accordance with this scheme once the Commission is satisfied that such notice:

- is given on behalf of a proscribed organisation, and
 - provides the Commission with sufficient information to indicate a clear intention to decommission specified arms.
8. He will continue to act in accordance with the scheme only if he complies with all the requirements of this scheme and the arrangements provided for by it.
 9. A person who gives notice to the Commission in accordance with paragraph 7 above (“the contact person”) shall provide the Commission with such information as it may require for the purpose of making arrangements for decommissioning, and such information may include-
 - the name of the proscribed organisation proposing to decommission the arms,
 - the location where it is proposed that the arms should be collected by the Commission or destroyed by the person proposing to decommission them,
 - the number or quantity and type of the arms and information about their age and condition,

1. The extent of the amnesty period is currently constrained by section 2(2) of the Northern Ireland Arms Decommissioning Act 1997, as amended by the Northern Ireland Arms Decommissioning (Amendment) Act 2002 and the Northern Ireland Arms Decommissioning Act 1997 (Amnesty Period) Order 2004.

- an indication as to whether the arms will require to be moved to the location referred to above,
 - if the arms are to be collected by the Commission, the day on which and the time at which it is proposed the arms can be collected, and
 - any other information required by the Commission.
10. The Commission shall keep a record of all the information provided in accordance with paragraph 9.

Non-disclosure of information

11. A person who has provided information to the Commission in accordance with this scheme shall not intentionally disclose that information to any person who is not acting with him without the agreement of the Commission nor do anything which affects the accuracy of the information which has been provided. If he subsequently becomes aware of any matter which affects the accuracy of the information provided, he shall inform the Commission as soon as practicable. The Commission shall keep a record of any such information provided to it.

Making of arrangements by the Commission for the purpose of decommissioning arms and ensuring public safety

12. The Commission may make such arrangements as it considers appropriate to facilitate the decommissioning of arms in accordance with this scheme including requiring compliance with any conditions necessary on grounds of public safety.
13. Persons who are acting with the contact person on behalf of the proscribed organisation, act in accordance with this scheme if they comply with all the requirements of the scheme and the arrangements provided by it.
14. Nothing shall be done with arms in respect of which contact has been with the Commission under paragraph 7 above which is not necessary in order to comply with arrangements made or conditions imposed by the Commission.

Locations at which decommissioning of arms may take place

15. The locations at which the decommissioning of arms may take place shall be determined in accordance with arrangements made by the Commission.

Movement of arms

16. The movement of any arms for the purpose of decommissioning them to a location determined under paragraph 15 by a person other than the

Commission shall be in accordance with arrangements made by the Commission and subject to compliance with any conditions imposed by the Commission.

17 Without prejudice to the generality of paragraph 16, the conditions which the Commission may impose may relate to:

- the location to which arms may be moved,
- the quantity of arms which may be moved at any one time,
- the method of transportation to be used, and
- the condition in which the arms may be transported including the requirement that there shall be no movement of arms by public transport, movement of primed explosives or movement of loaded firearms.

The Commission may, on grounds of public safety, prohibit the movement of specified arms or specified types of arms.

18. The Commission shall keep a record of any conditions imposed in accordance with paragraph 17.

19. Where the Commission has agreed the conditions on which movement may take place, it may give to a person moving arms in accordance with this scheme a document stating that the arms described in the document are being moved by the person under arrangement made by the Commission. A copy shall be retained by the Commission.

20. A person moving arms in accordance with this scheme shall inform the Commission of the arrival of the arms at the location agreed with the Commission unless the Commission has taken part in the movement of the arms in question or is already at the location when the arms arrive there.

Destruction of arms by the Commission

21. Where information has been provided for the purpose of collection and destruction by the Commission, the Commission shall

- carry out, or arrange to have carried out, an evaluation of the arms involved to determine their stability and whether it is safe to move or destroy them,
- collect or supervise the collection of the arms and, if appropriate, their movement to another location for destruction, and

- destroy, or supervise the destruction of the arms and dispose, or supervise the disposal, of any resulting residue.
22. Where arms are to be destroyed by persons in unlawful possession
- the person or persons concerned shall destroy the arms in accordance with arrangements made with the Commission, and
 - the Commission shall dispose, or supervise the disposal, of any resulting residue.
23. Destruction of arms by the Commission shall mean:
- in the case of firearms, them being rendered unusable as weapons by methods such as cutting, bending, chipping, stamping and grinding and the disposal of the residue;
 - in the case of ammunition or explosives, their burning, firing, discharge, detonation or disposal by other means.
24. Before destroying any arms, the Commission shall log details of the arms including:
- in the case of firearms, the number, type and make (if known),
 - in the case of ammunition or explosives, the quantity, make (if known) and, in the case of ammunition, the calibre,
 - the name of the proscribed organisation by whom the arms are being decommissioned, and
 - such particulars of the decommissioning process (including the date, time and location and relevant events or processes) as the Commission considers necessary to ensure a complete record of the decommissioning process.

Where arms are destroyed by a person other than the Commission and without the Commission's supervision in accordance with this scheme the person shall make a record containing the information specified in this paragraph (other than the particulars of the decommissioning process referred to above) and shall give the information to the Commission. Where necessary and to the extent possible the Commission will verify the information given to it by a person who has destroyed arms by examining any residue resulting from the destruction.

Presence of persons at decommissioning events

25. Where arms are decommissioned in accordance with this scheme, the Commission may allow the person or persons decommissioning them, or an intermediary of that person or persons, to be present at the collection and destruction of the arms or the disposal of any resulting residue subject to compliance by the person or persons with any conditions imposed by the Commission.

In this paragraph “intermediary”, in relation to a person, means a person authorised by the first mentioned person to act on the person's behalf, being an authorisation notice of which has been given to the Commission.

Confidentiality

26. The Commission shall ensure that all information received by it in relation to the decommissioning process is kept confidential and that any records maintained by the Commission are kept secure. Disclosure of information received by the Commission may occur where disclosure is necessary:

- for reasons of public safety,
- to confirm the legitimate participation in the decommissioning process by those eligible to do so,
- to fulfil the Commission's duty to report to the two Governments.

[Signed]

ADAM INGRAM
For and on behalf of the Secretary of State
Northern Ireland Office
29 June 1998

STATUTORY INSTRUMENTS

S.I. No. 216 of 1998

DECOMMISSIONING ACT, 1997 (DECOMMISSIONING) REGULATIONS, 1998

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DECOMMISSIONING ACT, 1997 (DECOMMISSIONING) REGULATIONS, 1998

WHEREAS the Government and the Government of the United Kingdom by an agreement between them done on the 26th day of August, 1997, established the Independent International Commission on Decommissioning ("the Commission");

AND WHEREAS it is enacted by section 2(1) of the Decommissioning Act, 1997 (No. 3 of 1997), that regulations may provide for the decommissioning of arms;

AND WHEREAS it is provided by section 4(2)(g) of the said Act that regulations may provide for the functions of the Commission and its role generally in relation to the decommissioning of arms or any particular method or manner of such decommissioning;

AND WHEREAS the Commission, in accordance with Article 4 of the said agreement and the Decommissioning Act, 1997 (Independent International Commission on Decommissioning) Regulations, 1997 (S.I. No. 400 of 1997), consulted with the participants in political negotiations in Northern Ireland, including the Government and the Government of the United Kingdom, and other persons whom it deemed relevant, in relation to the type of scheme or schemes for the decommissioning of arms that should be made and the role it might play under and in respect of any such scheme or schemes;

AND WHEREAS the Commission, also in accordance with the said Article 4 and the said Regulations, has presented to the Government and the Government of the United Kingdom proposals for such schemes;

AND WHEREAS the Minister for Justice, Equality and Law Reform proposes, for the purposes inter alia of such schemes, to make the following Regulations;

NOW, I, JOHN O'DONOGHUE, Minister for Justice, Equality and Law Reform, in exercise of the powers conferred on me by section 7(1) of the Decommissioning Act, 1997 (No. 3 of 1997), and the Justice (Alteration of Name of Department and Title of Minister) Order, 1997 (S.I. No. 298 of 1997), hereby make the following Regulations:

Preliminary

1. These Regulations may be cited as the Decommissioning Act, 1997 (Decommissioning) Regulations, 1998.
2. These Regulations shall come into operation on the 30th day of June, 1998, and shall expire on the 22nd day of May, 2000.

Interpretation

3. (1) In these Regulations -

"the Commission" means the Independent International Commission on Decommissioning established by an agreement between the Government and the Government of the United Kingdom done on the 26th day of August, 1997, and, in

Regulations 10, 11, 12 and 13, includes any person, duly authorised by the Commission to perform on its behalf the functions of the Commission under those Regulations;

"contact person" means a person who has given notice to the Commission in accordance with Regulation 6(1);

"intermediary", in relation to a person, means a person authorised by the first-mentioned person to act on the person's behalf, being an authorisation notice of which has been given to the Commission;

"paramilitary organisation" means -

- (a) an unlawful organisation (within the meaning of the Offences against the State Act, 1939 (No. 13 of 1939)) in respect of which a suppression order under that Act is in force, or
- (b) a proscribed organisation for the purposes of the Act of the British Parliament entitled the Northern Ireland (Emergency Provisions) Act 1996.

(2) In these Regulations -

- (a) a reference to a Regulation is a reference to a Regulation of these Regulations, unless it is indicated that reference to some other provision is indicated, and

- (b) a reference to a paragraph is a reference to a paragraph of the provision in which the reference occurs, unless it is indicated that reference to some other provision is intended.

Methods and manners by and in which the decommissioning of arms may take place

4. Decommissioning of arms may take place -
- (a) by the provision of information to the Commission leading to the collection and destruction of the arms by the Commission, or
 - (b) by the destruction of the arms by those in possession of them.

Provision of information by the Commission

5. The Commission may provide a person who seeks information from it in relation to the decommissioning of arms or the application of these Regulations such information as it considers appropriate.

Notice of intention to decommission arms

6. (1) A person who proposes to decommission arms on behalf of a paramilitary organisation in accordance with Regulation 4 or an intermediary of that person shall, before doing any other act leading to their decommissioning, give notice to the Commission of the proposal in accordance with arrangements made by the Commission.

(2) The process of decommissioning any particular arms shall be deemed to commence on the receipt by the Commission of notice under this Regulation as respects which the Commission is satisfied that it -

- (a) is given on behalf of a paramilitary organisation, and
- (b) contains sufficient information to indicate a clear intention to decommission specified arms.

Provision of information to Commission

7. (1) A contact person shall provide the Commission with such information as it may require for the purpose of making arrangements for the decommissioning concerned.

(2) Without prejudice to the generality of paragraph (1), information required under that paragraph may include -

- (a) the name of the paramilitary organisation proposing to decommission the arms concerned,
- (b) the location where it is proposed that the arms concerned should be collected by the Commission or destroyed by the person proposing to decommission them,

- (c) the number or quantity and type of the arms concerned and information about their age and condition,
 - (d) an indication as to whether the arms concerned will require to be moved to the location referred to in subparagraph (b), and
 - (e) if the arms concerned are to be collected by the Commission, the day on which and the time at which it is proposed that the collection should take place.
- (3) A person who has provided information to the Commission in accordance with paragraph (2) -
- (a) shall not intentionally disclose any of the information to a person who is not acting with him in relation to the proposal aforesaid without the agreement of the Commission,
 - (b) shall not do anything which affects the accuracy of the information provided, and
 - (c) if he becomes aware of any matter that affects the accuracy of the information provided, inform the Commission of that matter as soon as practicable.

(4) The Commission shall keep a record of information provided in accordance with paragraphs (2) and (3).

Making of arrangements by the Commission for the purpose of decommissioning arms and ensuring public safety

8. (1) The Commission may make such arrangements as it considers appropriate to facilitate the decommissioning of arms in accordance with the Act and these Regulations and may impose such conditions in relation to the decommissioning of arms as it considers necessary on grounds of public safety.

(2) Persons taking part in the process of decommissioning arms -

(a) shall act in accordance with any arrangements made under these Regulations and shall comply with any conditions imposed under them, and

(b) shall not do anything, or permit anything to be done, in relation to the decommissioning of arms that is not necessary for the purpose of compliance with these Regulations.

Location at which the decommissioning of arms may take place

9. The locations at which the decommissioning of arms may take place shall be determined in accordance with arrangements made by the Commission.

Movement of arms prior to their collection by the Commission or their destruction by those in possession of them

10. (1) The movement of any arms for the purpose of decommissioning them to a location determined pursuant to Regulation 9 by a person other than the Commission shall be in accordance with arrangements made by the Commission and subject to compliance by the person with any conditions imposed by the Commission.

(2) The Commission may, on grounds of public safety, prohibit the movement of specified arms or specified types of arms.

(3) Without prejudice to the generality of paragraph (1), conditions which the Commission may impose may relate to -

- (a) the location to which arms may be moved,
- (b) the quantity of arms which may be moved at any one time,
- (c) the method of transportation to be used, and
- (d) the condition in which arms may be moved,

and may include a condition that firearms are unloaded and explosives and explosive substances are unprimed when being moved and that arms are not moved by means of public transport.

(4) Where the Commission has agreed arrangements under which the movement of arms may take place, it may give a person moving arms in accordance with the arrangements a document showing that the arms described in the document are, for the purpose of decommissioning them, being moved by the person under arrangements made by the Commission.

(5) The Commission shall keep a record of any conditions imposed in accordance with paragraph (1) and a copy of any document issued in accordance with paragraph (4).

(6) A person moving arms in accordance with this Regulation shall inform the Commission of the arrival of the arms at the location designated in accordance with Regulation 9 unless the Commission has taken part in the movement of the arms in question or is already at the location when the arms arrive there.

Recording of information before destruction of arms

11. (1) Before the destruction by the Commission or subject to its supervision of any particular arms in connection with their decommissioning in accordance with Regulation 4, the Commission shall make, or arrange for the making and delivery to it of, a record containing the following information:

(a) in the case of firearms, the number and type or types and, if known or ascertainable, the make or makes of the firearms,

- (b) in the case of ammunition, explosives or explosive substances, the quantity and, if known, the make or makes of the ammunition, explosives or explosive substances and, in the case of ammunition, the calibre or calibres of the ammunition,
- (c) the name of the organisation by whom the arms are being decommissioned, and
- (d) such particulars of the decommissioning process (including the date, time and location of relevant events or processes) as the Commission considers necessary to ensure a complete record of the decommissioning process.

(2) Before the destruction of any particular arms by a person other than the Commission, and without the supervision of the Commission, for the purpose of decommissioning them in accordance with these Regulations, the person shall make a record containing the information specified in subparagraphs (a), (b) and (c) of paragraph (1) and shall transmit it, or a copy of it, to the Commission.

(3) Where necessary and to the extent possible, the Commission shall verify the information in a record made under paragraph (2) by examining any residue resulting from the destruction of the arms concerned.

Collection and destruction of arms decommissioned in accordance with Regulation 4(a) and disposal of residue

12. Where arms fall to be decommissioned in accordance with Regulation 4(a) -

- (a) the Commission shall carry out, or arrange to have carried out, an evaluation of the arms involved to determine their stability and whether it is safe to move or destroy them,
- (b) the Commission shall, if appropriate, collect or supervise the collection of the arms and their movement to another location for destruction, and
- (c) the Commission shall destroy, or supervise the destruction of, the arms and dispose, or supervise the disposal, of any resulting residue.

Destruction of arms decommissioned in accordance with Regulation 4(b) and disposal of residue

13. Where arms fall to be decommissioned in accordance with Regulation 4(b) -

- (a) the person or persons concerned shall destroy the arms in accordance with arrangements made with the Commission, and
- (b) the Commission shall dispose, or supervise the disposal, of any resulting residue.

Presence of persons at decommissioning events

14. (1) Where arms fall to be decommissioned in accordance with Regulation 4(a), the Commission may allow the person or persons decommissioning the arms or an intermediary of the person or persons to be present at the collection and destruction of the arms and the disposal of any resulting residue subject to compliance by the person or persons with any conditions imposed by the Commission.

(2) Where arms fall to be decommissioned in accordance with Regulation 4(b), the Commission may allow the person or persons decommissioning the arms or an intermediary of the person or persons to be present at the disposal of any resulting residue subject to compliance by the person or persons with any conditions imposed by the Commission.

Destruction of arms

15. The destruction of arms pursuant to Regulation 12 or 13 shall be effected -

- (a) in the case of firearms, by their being rendered unusable as weapons by methods such as cutting, bending, chipping, stamping and grinding and by the disposal of the residue, and
- (b) in the case of ammunition, explosives and explosive substances, by their being burned, fired, discharged, detonated or disposed of by other means.

Confidentiality

16. (1) Subject to paragraph (2), the Commission shall ensure that all information received by it in relation to the decommissioning process is kept confidential and that any records maintained by the Commission are kept secure.

(2) The Commission may disclose information received by it where such disclosure is necessary -

- (a) for reasons of public safety,
- (b) to confirm the legitimate participation in the decommissioning process by those eligible to so participate, or
- (c) to discharge the duty of the Commission to report to the Government and the Government of the United Kingdom.

GIVEN under my Official Seal,

this 29th day of June, 1998

John O'Donoghue

MINISTER FOR JUSTICE,

EQUALITY AND LAW REFORM

EXPLANATORY NOTE

(This note is not part of the instrument and does not purport to be a legal interpretation).

These regulations make provision for the decommissioning of arms and for the functions of the Independent International Commission in relation to such decommissioning in accordance with sections 2 and 4(2)(g) of the Decommissioning Act, 1997.

Decommissioning Scheme based on Section 3(1) of the Northern Ireland Arms Decommissioning Act 1997

Introduction

1. This is a decommissioning scheme within the meaning of section 1 of the Northern Ireland Arms Decommissioning Act 1997 ("the 1997 Act") made by the Secretary of State to facilitate the decommissioning of firearms, ammunition and explosives ("arms") in Northern Ireland. It supplements the scheme made by the Secretary of State on 29 June 1998 and it comes into force on 3 August 2001.
2. The scheme makes provision for the decommissioning of arms in accordance with section 3 of the 1997 Act by making them permanently inaccessible or permanently unusable.
3. The period during which arms may be dealt with in accordance with the scheme ends with [24 February 2005].
4. Unless the contrary intention appears, expressions used in the scheme have the same meaning as in the 1997 Act, and-
 - (a) "the Commission" means the independent International Commission established by agreement between the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland and the Republic of Ireland made on 27 August 1997 and includes any person authorised by the Commission to perform functions on its behalf;
 - (b) "proscribed organisation" means an organisation specified in Schedule 2 to the Terrorism Act 2000;
 - (c) "contact person" means a person who has given notice to the Commission on behalf of a proscribed organisation of a proposal to make arms permanently inaccessible or permanently unusable.

Provision of information by the Commission

5. The Commission may provide to a person who seeks it such information in relation to the making of arms permanently inaccessible or permanently unusable in accordance with this scheme as it considers appropriate.

Notice of intention to decommission arms

- 6.(1) Notice of a proposal to make arms permanently inaccessible or permanently unusable must be given to the Commission by a contact person in accordance with arrangements determined by the Commission before any other act leading to decommissioning is undertaken.
- (2) Decommissioning under this scheme may only begin if the Commission is satisfied that the notice-
 - (a) is given on behalf of a proscribed organisation, and
 - (b) contains sufficient information to indicate a clear intention to make specified arms permanently inaccessible and permanently unusable.

Information provided to the Commission

- 7.(1) A contact person must provide the Commission with such information as it may require in relation to a proposal to make arms permanently inaccessible and permanently unusable.
- (2) A person who provides information to the Commission under paragraph (1) must not-
 - (a) intentionally disclose any of it, without the Commission's consent, to a person who is not acting with him;
 - (b) subject to paragraph (3), do anything which affects its accuracy.
- (3) The Commission must be informed as soon as possible of any matter which may affect the accuracy of information provided under paragraph (1).
- (4) The Commission must keep a record of information provided under paragraph (1).

Arrangements for decommissioning

- 8.(1) The Commission may make such arrangements with a contact person or a person acting with him as it considers appropriate to facilitate the making of arms permanently inaccessible or permanently unusable.
- (2) The arrangements referred to in paragraph (1) may include conditions considered necessary on grounds of public safety.
- (3) A person acting to make arms permanently inaccessible or permanently unusable in accordance with this scheme must comply with the arrangements and conditions referred to in paragraphs (1) and (2).

Locations at which decommissioning of arms may take place

9. The locations at which the making of arms permanently inaccessible or permanently unusable may take place are to be determined in accordance with arrangements made by the Commission with the contact person or a person acting with him.

Movement of arms

- 10.(1) Where arms are moved for the purpose of making them permanently inaccessible or permanently unusable to a location determined by a person other than the Commission, such movement must be in accordance with arrangements made by the Commission and subject to any conditions considered necessary on grounds of public safety.
- (2) The conditions referred to in paragraph (1) may include conditions about-
 - (a) the location to which arms may be moved,
 - (b) the quantity of arms which may be moved at a time,
 - (c) the method of transportation, and
 - (d) the condition in which arms may be moved, including conditions that arms must be unloaded, explosives must be unprimed and that public transport must not be used.
- (3) Where arms are moved in accordance with arrangements made under paragraph (1), the Commission may give to any person moving them a document showing that they are moved for the purpose of making them permanently inaccessible or permanently unusable in accordance with this scheme.
- (4) The Commission must keep a record of any arrangements made under paragraph (1), any conditions imposed on grounds of public safety and any document issued under paragraph (3).
- (5) The Commission must be informed of the arrival of any arms moved under paragraph (1).

Records of decommissioned arms

- 11.(1) Where arms are made permanently inaccessible or permanently unusable in accordance with this scheme, the Commission must-
 - (a) make a record of the arms containing such information as it considers necessary, or

- (b) arrange for the contact person or a person acting with him to provide it with such a record.
- (2) The Commission must take such steps as are necessary to verify the information contained in a record provided under paragraph 1(b).

Method of making permanently inaccessible or permanently unusable

- 12. The method by which arms are to be made permanently inaccessible or permanently unusable, so that they are completely beyond use, is to be determined by the Commission after consultation with the contact person or a person acting with him.

John Reid

Secretary of State for Northern Ireland
2 August 2001

**DECOMMISSIONING ACT, 1997 (DECOMMISSIONING) (SUPPLEMENTARY)
REGULATIONS, 2001**

WHEREAS the Government and the Government of the United Kingdom, by an agreement between them done on the 26th day of August, 1997, established the Independent International Commission on Decommissioning ("the Commission");

AND WHEREAS it is enacted by section 2(1) of the Decommissioning Act, 1997 (No. 3 of 1997) that regulations may provide for the decommissioning of arms;

AND WHEREAS it is provided by section 4(2)(g) and (h) of the said Act that regulations may provide for the functions of the Commission and its role generally in relation to the decommissioning of arms or any particular method or manner of such decommissioning, and for any other matters that the Minister for Justice, Equality and Law Reform considers necessary for the purposes of the Act;

AND WHEREAS regulations (the Decommissioning Act, 1997 (Decommissioning) Regulations, 1998 to 2001) have been made under the said provisions of the said Act providing for methods and manners of decommissioning of arms, and the role of the Commission in relation to these;

AND WHEREAS the Government have consulted with the Commission on making supplementary provision for the decommissioning of arms to facilitate the process of decommissioning;

AND WHEREAS as a consequence the Minister for Justice, Equality and Law Reform proposes to make the following Regulations;

NOW I, John O'Donoghue, Minister for Justice, Equality and Law Reform, in exercise of the powers conferred on me by section 7(1) of the Decommissioning Act, 1997 (No. 3 of 1997), and the Justice (Alteration of Name of Department and Title of Minister) Order, 1997 (S.I. No. 298 of 1997), make the following Regulations:

Preliminary

1. These Regulations may be cited as the Decommissioning Act, 1997 (Decommissioning) (Supplementary) Regulations, 2001.

2. These Regulations shall come into operation on the 3rd day of August 2001, and shall expire on the 27th day of February, 2002.

Interpretation

3. (1) In these Regulations -

"the Act" means the Decommissioning Act, 1997;

"the Commission" means the Independent International Commission on Decommissioning established by an agreement between the Government and the Government of the United Kingdom done on the 26th day of August, 1997, and, in Regulations 10 and 11, includes any person duly authorised by the Commission to perform on its behalf the functions of the Commission under those Regulations;

"contact person" means a person who has given notice to the Commission in accordance with Regulation 6(1);

"intermediary", in relation to a person, means a person authorised by the first-mentioned person to act on the person's behalf, being an authorisation notice of which has been given to the Commission;

"paramilitary organisation" means -

- (a) an unlawful organisation (within the meaning of the Offences against the State Act, 1939 (No. 13 of 1939), in respect of which a suppression order under that Act is in force, or

- (b) a proscribed organisation for the purposes of the Act of the British Parliament entitled the Terrorism Act 2000.
- (2) In these Regulations -
- (a) a reference to a Regulation is a reference to a Regulation of these Regulations, unless it is indicated that reference to some other provision is intended, and
 - (b) a reference to a paragraph is a reference to a paragraph of the provision in which the reference occurs, unless it is indicated that reference to some other provision is intended.

Methods and manners by and in which the decommissioning of arms may take place

4. Decommissioning of arms may take place by making the arms permanently inaccessible or unusable.

Provision of information by the Commission

5. The Commission may provide to a person who seeks information from it in relation to making arms permanently inaccessible or unusable or the application of these Regulations such information as it considers appropriate.

Notice of intention to make arms permanently inaccessible or unusable

6. (1) A person who proposes to make arms permanently inaccessible or unusable on behalf of a paramilitary organisation in accordance with Regulation 4, or an intermediary of that person, shall, before doing any other act leading to their being made permanently inaccessible or unusable, give notice to the Commission of the proposal in accordance with arrangements made with the Commission.

(2) The process of making any particular arms permanently inaccessible or unusable shall be deemed to commence on the receipt by the Commission of notice under this Regulation as respects which the Commission is satisfied that it -

(a) is given on behalf of a paramilitary organisation, and

(b) contains sufficient information to indicate a clear intention to make specified arms permanently inaccessible or unusable.

Provision of information to Commission

7. (1) A contact person shall provide the Commission with such information as it may require in relation to the proposal to make arms permanently inaccessible or unusable.

(2) A person who has provided information to the Commission in accordance with paragraph (1) -

(a) shall not intentionally disclose any of the information to a person who is not acting with him or her in relation to the proposal aforesaid without the agreement of the Commission,

(b) shall not do anything which affects the accuracy of the information provided, and

(c) if he or she becomes aware of any matter that affects the accuracy of the information provided, inform the Commission of that matter as soon as practicable.

(3) The Commission shall keep a record of information provided in accordance with paragraphs (1) and (2)(c).

Making of arrangements for the purpose of making arms permanently inaccessible or unusable and ensuring public safety

8. (1) The Commission may make such arrangements with a contact person, or an intermediary of that person, as it considers appropriate to facilitate the making of arms permanently inaccessible or unusable in accordance with the Act and these Regulations and may agree with a contact person, or an intermediary of that person, such conditions in relation to making arms permanently inaccessible or unusable as it considers necessary on grounds of public safety.

(2) Persons taking part in the process of making arms permanently inaccessible or unusable shall act in accordance with any arrangements made under these Regulations and any conditions agreed under paragraph (1).

Location at which the making of arms permanently inaccessible or unusable may take place

9. The locations at which the making of arms permanently inaccessible or unusable may take place shall be determined in accordance with arrangements made between the Commission and the contact person concerned, or an intermediary of that person.

Movement of arms prior to their being made permanently inaccessible or unusable

10. (1) The movement of any arms for the purpose of making them permanently inaccessible or unusable to a location determined pursuant to Regulation 9 by a person other than the Commission shall be in accordance with arrangements made by the Commission with that person and subject to any conditions agreed by the Commission with that person.

(2) The Commission may, on grounds of public safety, prohibit the movement of specified arms or specified types of arms.

(3) Without prejudice to the generality of paragraph (1), conditions agreed under that paragraph may relate to -

- (a) the location to which arms may be moved,
- (b) the quantity of arms which may be moved at any one time,
- (c) the method of transportation to be used, and
- (d) the condition in which arms may be moved,

and may include a condition that firearms are unloaded and explosives and explosive substances are unprimed when being moved and that arms are not moved by means of public transport.

(4) Where the Commission has agreed arrangements under which the movement of arms may take place, it may give a person moving arms in accordance with the arrangements a document showing that the arms described in the document are, for the purpose of making them permanently inaccessible or unusable, being moved by the person under arrangements made by the Commission.

(5) The Commission shall keep a record of any conditions agreed under paragraph (1) and a copy of any document issued in accordance with paragraph (4).

(6) A person moving arms in accordance with this Regulation shall inform the Commission of the arrival of the arms at the location determined in accordance with Regulation 9 unless the Commission has taken part in the movement of the arms in question or is at the location when the arms arrive there.

Recording of information before making arms permanently inaccessible or unusable

11. (1) Before the making permanently inaccessible or unusable of any particular arms in accordance with these Regulations, the Commission shall make a record containing such information as it considers necessary in relation to those arms, or where appropriate shall arrange with the contact person concerned, or an intermediary of that person, for the making and delivery to it of such a record.

(2) Where necessary and to the extent possible, the Commission shall verify the information in a record delivered to it under paragraph (1) by inspection.

Making arms permanently inaccessible or unusable

12. The making of arms permanently inaccessible or unusable and the verification of such making shall be effected by such measures to make the arms no longer accessible or to put them completely beyond use as shall be determined by the Commission after consultation with the contact person concerned, or an intermediary of that person.

Confidentiality

13. (1) Subject to paragraph (2), the Commission shall ensure that all information received by it in relation to making arms permanently inaccessible or unusable is kept confidential and that any records maintained by the Commission are kept secure.

(2) The Commission may disclose information received by it where such disclosure is necessary -

(a) for reasons of public safety,

(b) to confirm the legitimate participation in the decommissioning process by those eligible to participate in it, or

- (c) to discharge the duty of the Commission to report to the Government and the Government of the United Kingdom.

GIVEN under my Official Seal,
this 3rd day of August 2001

John O'Donoghue
MINISTER FOR JUSTICE,
EQUALITY AND LAW REFORM

**FINAL REPORT OF THE
INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL
COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING**

**Presented to the Government of the United
Kingdom and the Government of Ireland
Published 4 July 2011**

INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING

Brigadier Tauno Nieminen

General John de Chastelain

Andrew D. Sens

28 March 2011

The Rt. Hon Owen Paterson, MP
Secretary of State for Northern Ireland

Alan Shatter, TD
Minister of Justice and Law Reform

FINAL REPORT OF THE INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING

Reference	A.	Report of the International Body, 22 January 1996
	B.	The Northern Ireland Arms Decommissioning Act 1997 (UK)
	C.	The Northern Ireland Arms Decommissioning Act 1997 (Ireland)
	D.	Agreement between the Government of Ireland and the Government of the United Kingdom Establishing the Independent International Commission on Decommissioning, 26 August 1997
	E.	Decommissioning Scheme, Northern Ireland Office, 29 June 1998
	F.	Decommissioning Regulations, Government of Ireland, 29 June 1998
	G.	Decommissioning Scheme, Northern Ireland Office, 2 August 2001
	H.	Decommissioning Regulations, Government of Ireland, 3 August 2001

INTRODUCTION

1. The British and Irish Governments have requested a Final Report from the Commission now that its mandate has ended. This is that report. The Commission's mandate began on 26 August 1997 in accordance with Reference D, which was brought into force on 24 September that year when the two Governments formally established the Commission. Legislation required that the mandate be renewed annually by both Governments to give the Commission immunity from prosecution to interact with proscribed organizations, and to give paramilitary groups amnesty to have their arms decommissioned without being used in evidence for prosecution. The mandate was extended annually over the following twelve years by both Governments, until their decision not to renew it in 2010. Thus it ended in Northern Ireland at midnight on Tuesday 9 February 2010 and in Ireland at midnight on Thursday 25 February 2010.

2. Where appropriate we have attached Annexes to this report. We have not included all the official documents or legislation pertaining to the Commission. Many of these are available through a number of sources open to the public and all of them are already in the possession of the Governments. However for convenience we have cited certain official documents as References and we have attached them as Annexes to this report.

3. We have not included with this report copies of correspondence sent to the Commission by private individuals as these might be subject to privacy considerations. Also as directed by Ref. D, we consulted with the Northern Ireland political parties at the outset of our mandate and received from them papers setting out their views on decommissioning. These were provided in confidence and along with the private correspondence they will be deposited with our files for safekeeping by Boston College, Massachusetts, USA, subject to an embargo on their disclosure for thirty years.

OUTLINE

4. The report is comprised under the following headings:

- a. Mandate
- b. Organization
- c. Consultation
- d. Liaison
- e. Reporting
- f. Decommissioning: General
- g. Decommissioning: The Political Dimension
- h. Decommissioning: Chronology
- i. Reflections on the Process
- j. Lessons Learned
- k. Future arms decommissioning
- l. Conclusion

5. In their April 16th 2010 letter to the Commission requesting this report, the Governments listed issues they wished to see addressed in addition to those we would routinely include. These are addressed under the headings noted in subparagraphs 4.i., 4.j. and 4.k. above.

MANDATE

6. In brief, the Commission's *mandate* as directed in legislation and in supplementary Government directions was to:

- a. Consult widely;
- b. Recommend decommissioning methodology to the two Governments;
- c. Execute the decommissioning of paramilitary arms; and
- d. Report to the two Governments.

7. As detailed in Article 3 of Ref. D, the Commission was charged to: *facilitate the decommissioning of firearms, ammunition, explosives and explosive substances (hereinafter referred to as "arms") in accordance with the Report of the International Body, and regulations or arrangements made under the Decommissioning Act 1997 and any decommissioning schemes within the meaning of section 1 of the Northern Ireland Arms Decommissioning Act 1997.*

8. Ref. D required the Commission to: *Present to the two Governments proposals for schemes for decommissioning having due regard to the views expressed by those it has consulted.* After consultation with the two Governments, with the Northern Ireland political parties represented in the Decommissioning Sub-Committee of the Plenary Session, with the spokesman representing the Ulster Volunteer Force (UVF) and the Red Hand Commando (RHC), and with those the Commission believed could pass on the views of the other main paramilitary groups then on ceasefire, the Commission recommended two of the decommissioning options that had been suggested in the report of the International Body and reflected in Section 3 of Reference B and Section 2 of Reference C. These included:

- a. Provision of information for the purpose of collection and destruction by the Commission or a designated person; and
- b. Destruction by persons in unlawful possession (with verification provided by the Commission).

9. On 15 January 1998 the Commission recommended these two methods of decommissioning to the Governments (ANNEX I and J) and these were subsequently incorporated into a decommissioning *Scheme* by the British Government (Reference E) and in decommissioning *Regulations* by the Government of Ireland (Reference F), which gave the Commission direction and authority to conduct the decommissioning of paramilitary arms in both jurisdictions. The Arms Decommissioning Acts (References B and C) defined *decommissioning* as the destruction of arms, and *destruction* was further defined as *making (arms) permanently inaccessible or permanently unusable*. The *Scheme* and *Regulations* were to be implemented accordingly. A subsequent decommissioning *Scheme*, supplementing the 29 June 1998 *Scheme*, was brought into force by the Secretary of State on 2 August 2001 (Reference G) and subsequent decommissioning *Regulations*, supplementing the 29 June 1998 *Regulations*, were brought into force by the Minister of Justice Equality and Law Reform on 3 August 2001 (Reference H).

10. Article 4 of Reference D also directed the Commission to report periodically to both Governments, as well as to verify and audit (make a record of) the arms decommissioned by it.

ORGANIZATION

11. **Personnel.** Reflecting its international construct and mirroring the composition of the International Body and the Office of the Independent Chairmen, the Commission's members were all drawn from Canada, Finland and the United States of America. Drivers and building security personnel were drawn from nationals in each jurisdiction. At the outset the Commission consisted of three Commissioners, three Assistants, four office staff members and three locally employed drivers. Later the numbers were reduced to three Commissioners, one Assistant, a budget and administrative aide, a part-time office staff member, and two locally employed drivers. The three Commissioners were not permanently located in theatre but travelled from their home countries in the execution of their function. The Assistant, the budget and administrative aide, and the part-time office staff member were based in Northern Ireland or Ireland.

12. **Offices.** The Commission, being an organization established by the two Governments, had offices in both jurisdictions. The Dublin Office was located at Dublin Castle and the Belfast office was located at Stormont Estate, initially in Rosepark House and subsequently in Knockview Buildings. One Commissioner and the budget and administrative aide were located in the Dublin office, supported by one locally-employed driver. Two Commissioners, the Assistant and the part-time office staff member were located in the Belfast office, supported by one locally-employed driver. Security of both offices was provided by the Governments.

13. **Finance.** Being an independent organization, the Commission was self-accounting and managed its own budget, which was audited on an annual basis. The Government of Ireland acted on behalf of both Governments in the allocation of the budget, costs of which were shared by each, and audit was also the responsibility of the Irish Government. The Commissioner located in Dublin was responsible for overseeing the management of the budget, and the budget and administrative aide in Dublin worked with Irish officials in its day to day accounting. The Commission's financial records are held by the Government of Ireland.

14. **Agents of the Commission.** As foreseen in the legislation, the two Governments had the option of naming Agents of the Commission. They did so in 2000, when they named Cyril Ramaphosa of South Africa and Martti Ahtisaari of Finland as Agents to examine arms dumps belonging to the Irish Republican Army (IRA) to confirm that the arms contained in them were not in use. This action was intended as a confidence building measure in the absence of actual decommissioning activity by that paramilitary group. As Agents, the two were independent, but they reported to the two Governments through the Commission, twice in 2000 – on 26 June and 26 October and once in 2001 – on 30 May. After the first IRA arms decommissioning act in 2001 the two ceased their role as Agents. During some of the decommissioning acts verified by the Commission, the paramilitary group concerned requested that independent witnesses be present. The witnesses were not declared to be Agents of the Commission, but both Governments agreed that equivalent immunities would apply in practice for dealing with proscribed organizations during the period they acted as witnesses.

15. **Explosive Ordnance Disposal.** As a measure of its independent role, and to give it the professional capability to deal safely with paramilitary ammunition, explosives and explosive substances, the Commission approached the Governments of Canada and the United States of America to provide EOD officers to assist the Commission, as and when needed. These officers were provided by the United States Army and the Bureau of Alcohol, Tobacco, Firearms and Explosives (BATFE), as well as by the Canadian Armed Forces. They were provided at no charge to the Commission, other than transportation and accommodation costs, and a number of them were subsequently involved in decommissioning events with the Commission. The Commission is grateful to Canada and the USA for the provision of these officers who did valuable and necessary work in the execution of the decommissioning mandate.

CONSULTATION

16. The Commission has consulted with both Governments on a regular basis since it was brought into being in 1997. Consultation was with representatives of the Northern Ireland Office in Belfast and London and with representatives of the Department of Justice and Law Reform in Dublin. Consultation took the form of regular meetings between the Commission and Government representatives, as well as, when called for, with the Secretary of State for Northern Ireland and the Minister of Justice and Law Reform.

17. As mentioned in paragraphs 3 and 8 above, we consulted with the political parties engaged in the talks through the means of the Decommissioning Sub-Committee of the Plenary Session. After the talks concluded with the Good Friday/Belfast Agreement in April 1998, we continued to meet with the Northern Ireland political parties, on request, until the Northern Ireland Assembly came into operation.

18. We also consulted with other agencies involved in the peace process, including the Patten Commission, the Police Oversight Commission and the Independent Monitoring Commission. We consulted with church groups and with various non-governmental organizations such as the Independent Commission for the Location of Victims' Remains, and we responded to correspondence from private citizens or groups that offered advice on decommissioning and on the disposal of decommissioned arms. As mentioned in paragraph 3 above, copies of correspondence exchanged between the Commission and private individuals are not included with this report but are being deposited with our files in Boston College.

LIAISON

19. During its operation, the Commission established a regular liaison link with the security agencies in both jurisdictions, including the Royal Ulster Constabulary (subsequently the Police Service of Northern Ireland) and the Army in Northern Ireland, and with the Garda Síochána and the Defence Forces in Ireland. We found that liaison with these organizations was vital to our function and we met on an as-required basis with liaison officers designated by each of the organizations. We benefited from their advice, from the regular provision of escorts when travelling on the public highway with arms to be decommissioned, with some aspects of decommissioning itself, and with searches carried out by the Commission based on information provided by paramilitary groups.

REPORTING

20. The Commission reported regularly to the representatives of the two Governments named for that purpose. The majority of the reporting was verbal, during consultative meetings, but written reports were also provided by us when the Governments requested them – on some occasions when we had carried out decommissioning acts. Copies of the written reports we provided to the Governments are included at ANNEX K.

DECOMMISSIONING: GENERAL

21. **Paramilitary Representatives.** When the Commission began its mandate in 1997 we recognized that we needed to interact with 'contact persons' from individual paramilitary groups who could represent to us authoritatively the views of their organization. The UVF and RHC jointly named a representative in late 1997 and the Loyalist Volunteer Force (LVF) did so in 1998, subsequent to the Good Friday/Belfast Agreement. Representatives of the IRA and the Ulster Defence Association (UDA) were named in late 1999, following the Review of the Agreement by Senator George Mitchell. The South East Antrim Brigade of the UDA, which split from the mainstream organization in 2007, named a representative that year, and the Official Irish Republican Army (OIRA) and the Irish National Liberation Army (INLA) each named representatives in 2008. In 2007 the Commission opened contact with the Shoukri paramilitary element which had been ousted from the UDA the previous year.

22. Our purpose in engaging with paramilitary representatives was to determine the willingness of the paramilitary groups concerned to decommission their arms, to agree on terms and methods of doing so that we felt met the requirements of our mandate (arms being rendered *permanently inaccessible or permanently unusable*), as well as to address questions of safety, completeness, verifiability and timings.

23. **Determining Terms and Methods of Decommissioning.** The Report of the International Body (Reference A) raised the need for arms decommissioning to be carried out in a manner that *should suggest neither victory nor defeat*, given that any decommissioning on the part of paramilitary groups would be voluntary acts. To that end we discussed with individual paramilitary group representatives:

- a. Whether the group wished to carry out decommissioning in public or in private;
- b. Whether the group wished cameras or witnesses to be present; and
- c. Whether the group or the Commission should be the first to make an act of decommissioning known publicly (noting that we had an obligation to inform the two Governments when such an act took place).

24. Only the LVF, which carried out an act of decommissioning in 1998, wished it to be executed in public with a media pool present. The other groups all wished their acts of decommissioning to be carried out in private with verification by the Commission. On occasion, some groups wished independent witnesses to be present.

25. **Paramilitary Arms.** In some instances estimates were available to the Commission of the quantity of arms held by individual paramilitary groups. These estimates identified the general nature of the weapons, ammunition, explosives or explosive devices believed to be held by individual groups, and possible quantities in a range between high and low figures. We considered the estimates as a guide during decommissioning. Representatives of each of the paramilitary groups (the LVF excepted) told us of the difficulties they had in confirming that the arms they decommissioned constituted the totality of the arms originally held by the group. Reasons given included:

- a. The passage of time and fading memories as to the locations of individual arms or caches;
- b. The fact that the organization had suffered a split and arms had been taken by those who had left;
- c. The distribution of arms to subordinate 'quartermasters' and the death of individuals who had been responsible for where arms were hidden;
- d. The recovery of arms by the security forces; and
- e. Imprecision in recalling the quantities of ammunition and explosives used in training and in paramilitary attacks.

26. In some cases the representatives of paramilitary groups told us where they believed arms they had been unable to find had originally been stored. We carried out searches in these areas, on occasion in cooperation with the security forces. With the concurrence of the paramilitary group concerned we have passed on to the security forces in both jurisdictions information regarding areas in which a paramilitary group believed some of its arms had been stored which it had been unable to recover.

27. Instances have occurred where a paramilitary group that decommissioned its arms, subsequently discovered previously un-recovered arms, and re-engaged with us to decommission them. In that regard, some paramilitary group representatives have asked us what they should do with arms they may

recover after the commission no longer exists. We refer that question to the Governments for their determination and we make suggestions commencing in paragraph 53 below.

28. Given the uncertain nature, or the absence of estimated arms holdings, when a paramilitary group declared it had completed decommissioning we asked its representative to confirm whether the arms decommissioned constituted its complete inventory. While each of the paramilitary groups we dealt with (the LVF excepted) confirmed that the arms they decommissioned constituted the totality of the arms under the leadership's control, none was able to confirm definitively that all of its arms had been decommissioned for the reasons listed in paragraph 25 above.

29. As required by direction from both jurisdictions (References D, E and F), the Commission has maintained a record of all the arms it verified as having been decommissioned. We are aware that by maintaining strict confidentiality with regard to arms decommissioned during the execution of our mandate (the LVF arms excepted) we caused concern to some in the wider political process. But we believe that decommissioning would not have been achieved had we not been able to maintain confidentiality about its conduct (paragraph 38 below).

30. While the reference direction is silent on the final disposition of the record of decommissioned arms, it has been our understanding from the outset that we would provide that record to the two governments for their information. We continue to believe that to be the right course of action, but we also believe that to do so now would be unhelpful to the peace process. Decommissioning is still incomplete in that armed and active paramilitary groups still possess a variety of arms. We have already referred to the issue of arms that come to light subsequent to the Commission's dissolution. Providing details now of what paramilitary arms have been put beyond use, could, in our opinion, encourage attacks on those groups which have taken risks for peace. This is true of both Loyalist and Republican paramilitary groups. We would not wish, inadvertently, to discourage future decommissioning events by groups that are actively engaged today, nor to deter groups that have decommissioned their arms from handing over any arms that may subsequently come to light.

31. Accordingly, we have made arrangements for the safe retention of the records of decommissioned arms by the United States Department of State in Washington, DC. The Department will hold them securely until such time as both the British and Irish Governments make a joint written request for them – when they consider it appropriate to do so, taking into consideration the prevailing circumstances and the issues we have identified here.

DECOMMISSIONING: THE POLITICAL DIMENSION

32. At no time did the Commission's mandate include a political remit. Its role was solely to execute paramilitary arms decommissioning and to report to the two Governments on it. But arms decommissioning itself was inextricably linked to political issues and its success or failure was dependant on progress in the political arena. In turn, progress or otherwise on decommissioning influenced events in the political arena. The reason that talks to address the future of politics in Northern Ireland did not begin immediately following the Republican and Loyalist ceasefires of 1994, was due to the issue of decommissioning. This failure led to the creation of the International Body to examine decommissioning and to make recommendations on it, but even after the Body's report was made public in January 1996, and even after the talks started the following June, the failure to reach agreement on anything other than procedural issues lasted for yet another year – largely over disagreement on where the issue of decommissioning should be placed on the Agenda. It was not until the Commission was established in 1997 to address the decommissioning problem, that the talks addressed substantive constitutional and political issues, leading to the Good Friday/Belfast Agreement

being concluded in April 1998 and subsequently approved in referendums North and South the following month.

33. Even then, progress in setting up the Assembly and devolving authority to it, was delayed by the lack of progress on decommissioning. A series of events whereby the Assembly was set up and then suspended, and then set up again and then suspended, occurred over a period of years, due in part to the lack of progress on decommissioning. From the onset of the Commission's establishment, we urged the paramilitary groups to make contact with us and to address decommissioning substantively. Even when all the groups had named representatives, progress on actual decommissioning lagged. We were given a number of reasons for the delay, some of them relating to political issues. These include:

a. **Timing.**

- (1) The decommissioning section of the Good Friday/Belfast Agreement states in part: *They (the Parties participating in the talks) also confirm their intention to continue to work constructively and in good faith with the Independent Commission, and to use any influence they may have, to achieve the decommissioning of all paramilitary arms within two years following endorsement in referendums North and South of the agreement and in the context of the implementation of the overall settlement.* Since the referendums took place in May 1998, the target date for decommissioning was May 2000. But other than the LVF decommissioning event in 1998, and despite our urgings to the other groups, no acts of decommissioning took place until 2001. Some of these groups reminded us that the Agreement called for decommissioning to take place: *in the context of the implementation of the overall settlement*, and pointed out that all aspects of the Agreement had not yet been implemented. Indeed, the implementation of the last major component of the Agreement – the devolution of policing and justice – only occurred early in 2010; and
- (2) As an aside, and not necessarily in connection with the political dimension of the delay in starting decommissioning, we also found that in some cases misperceptions caused delay. We were told by one loyalist paramilitary group shortly after the final IRA decommissioning event in 2005 that: “Everyone knew the IRA would never decommission, so we have not prepared our volunteers for this step.”

b. **Political Stability.** Other groups were cautious in agreeing to start decommissioning in light of what they observed to be the fragility of the political process. They reminded us that their groups had originally declared cease-fires in order to give politics the chance to address their concerns. But with the seemingly ‘on again, off again’ establishment and subsequent suspension of the Assembly, they were uncertain as to whether politics would indeed be able to address those concerns. In this regard we also believe that while the leadership of paramilitary groups on both sides was convinced that decommissioning and inclusive government was the way forward, they felt they had to move cautiously to ensure that their organizations did not split, and that called for demonstrable political progress; and

c. **Reintegration.** Some groups referred to the difficulty of reintegrating their paramilitary members into society, given that many had not completed their education or trades-training before joining their group, either before or during the period of the ‘Troubles’, and to the fact that the communities in which many lived were economically deprived

with few opportunities for employment. They sought recognition of these difficulties by the political authorities and action to address them, to encourage the membership to decommission their arms.

34. Although our ability to make progress on decommissioning was dependent on political issues outside our mandate, we did pass these concerns – expressed to us repeatedly and in detail by the representatives of some paramilitary groups – to the two Governments for their consideration.

DECOMMISSIONING: CHRONOLOGY

35. Numerous individual acts of decommissioning were carried out and verified by the Commission between 18 December 1998 and 8 February 2010. Written reports to the Governments on some decommissioning acts are among the reports included at Annex K. The chronology of these acts, and the related events between 1997 and 2010 are as follows:

- November 1997 – The UVF/RHC nominates a representative to the Commission.
- 10 April 1998 – The Good Friday/Belfast Agreement is concluded, calling for decommissioning within two years of referendums North and South on the Agreement.
- September 1998 – Sinn Féin nominates a representative to the Commission.
- 18 December 1998 – An act of decommissioning of some LVF arms is conducted by the Commission.
- 06 September to 19 November 1999 – The Mitchell Review of the Good Friday/Belfast Agreement takes place.
- 02 November 1999 – The Commission responds in writing to George Mitchell regarding decommissioning.
- November 1999 – The IRA and the UDA nominate representatives to the Commission, which commences separate discussions with them in December.
- November 1999 – The UVF/RHC representative agrees in general with proposed methods of decommissioning, but says they will not begin before the IRA has said “the war is over.” The Commission meets with four UDA representatives who generally agree on methods of decommissioning but claim they will not begin to decommission their arms before the IRA begins to do so.
- 30 November 1999 – The Northern Ireland Act 1998 devolves powers to the Northern Ireland Assembly with effect 2 December 1999.
- 11 February 2000 – The Commission reports it has received no information on when IRA decommissioning will start. The Secretary of State suspends the Assembly and reinstitutes Direct Rule. The IRA suspends contact with the Commission.
- 05 May 2000 – The two Governments make a joint statement to set up the Executive and to address the concerns about implementing the remaining issues of the Good Friday/Belfast Agreement. The decommissioning target of May 2000 having not been met, the two

Governments set a new target for decommissioning to be completed by June 2001. Subsequently the IRA propose, as a confidence building measure, to have outside observers examine some of their arms dumps to demonstrate that they are not being used. The governments call on Cyril Ramaphosa and Martti Ahtisaari to act as Agents to do this. The IRA agrees to resume discussions with the Commission.

- 30 May 2000 – Devolution of powers to the Northern Ireland Assembly is restored.
- 01 July 2001 – David Trimble resigns as First Minister over paramilitary failure to decommission, followed by the remaining UUP Ministers on 18 Oct.
- 10 August 2001 – The Secretary of State orders 24-hour suspensions of the Assembly between 10 August and 22 September 2001.
- 23 October 2001 – The IRA announces its first act of decommissioning.
- 06 November 2001 – David Trimble is re-elected as First Minister and Mark Durkan as Deputy First Minister.
- 08 April 2002 – The IRA's second act of decommissioning is announced.
- 14 October 2002 – The Secretary of State suspends the Assembly over allegations of Sinn Féin spying at the Assembly Building in Stormont.
- 30 October 2002 – The IRA states that its cease-fire is intact and that it is committed to the peace process, but that it is suspending its contact with the Commission. Contact was subsequently resumed.
- 17 January 2003 – The UVF suspends contact with the Commission due to concern over the lack of political progress.
- 28 April 2003 – The Assembly is formally dissolved in anticipation of a May 2003 election, which was subsequently postponed until later in the year.
- 21 October 2003 – The IRA's third act of decommissioning is announced.
- 26 November 2003 – An election in Northern Ireland produces a new Assembly, which is subsequently suspended.
- December 2004 – An anticipated fourth IRA decommissioning event is postponed over demands that photos be taken.
- 20 December 2004 – A large bank robbery takes place in Belfast, allegedly carried out by the IRA. Disagreement among political parties over the issue of decommissioning transparency derails progress on decommissioning by any of the paramilitary groups.
- April 2005 – The leader of Sinn Féin calls on the IRA to end its war and to decommission its arms.

- 28 July 2005 – The IRA publicly announces that “the war is over” and that it will decommission the remainder of its arms.
- 26 September 2005 – The Commission announces the completion of IRA arms decommissioning.
- 19 January 2006 – The Commission reports to the Governments that it has opened up discussions with the Ulster Political Review Group (UPRG) on behalf of the UDA, which will consider decommissioning if the Assembly will address its socio-economic concerns. The report also notes the UVF’s continuation of its break in formal discussions with the Commission.
- 15 May 2006 – The Secretary of State creates a non-legislative fixed-term Assembly to make preparations for the re-institution of a devolved government in Northern Ireland and for a fully restored Assembly.
- 13 October 2006 – The St Andrews Agreement leads to the establishment of a Transitional Assembly and a timetable to restore devolution, and sets the date for the third election to the Northern Ireland Assembly on 7 March 2007.
- 03 May 2007 – The UVF announces the abandonment of the use of violence in the pursuit of political aims. It declares it will put all its arms “beyond reach”, but not by decommissioning them through the Commission.
- 08 May 2007 – A new power-sharing Assembly is convened with the First and Deputy First Ministers taking office and a ten member Executive sworn in.
- 27 October 2007 – The Commission reports it has decommissioned a quantity of arms belonging to the South East Antrim Brigade of the UDA.
- 22 October 2008 – The Commission reports to the Governments that it has re-opened discussions with the UVF. The UDA representatives said their group wishes to decommission its arms but still waits for recognition of the economic concerns affecting its constituency. It is also concerned by the seeming political impasse within the Assembly. The representatives of the South East Antrim Brigade echoed similar sentiments concerning their members’ intention to decommission.
- 01 December 2008 – The Commission reports a decommissioning event involving some arms of the Shoukri paramilitary element.
- 29 January 2009 – The Governments announce the extension of the Commission’s mandate into February 2010, stating that this will be the last extension. They add the caveat that unless substantive progress is made on the decommissioning of loyalist weapons by August 2009, the mandate will be ended then.
- 12 June 2009 – The Commission reports verbally to the Governments that it has decommissioned substantial quantities of UVF/RHC arms in front of independent witnesses, and that the leadership of these paramilitary groups has declared that these arms constitute all they had under their control. The IICD also reports verbally that over the previous months it carried out a further two acts of decommissioning with the South East Antrim Brigade.

- 16 June 2009 – The Commission reports verbally to the Governments that it has carried out an act of decommissioning of UDA arms, which the representatives said was the first in a series of acts that should lead to their complete decommissioning.
- 18 October 2009 – The Official Irish Republican Army (OIRA) carries out an act of decommissioning with the Commission in front of independent witnesses.
- 17 December 2009 – The Irish National Liberation Army (INLA) carries out an act of decommissioning with the Commission in front of independent witnesses. The Commission also decommissions a second quantity of arms belonging to the Shoukri paramilitary element which we were informed was the remainder of those in its possession.
- 04 January 2010 – The OIRA carries out a second act of decommissioning. The representative states that the arms decommissioned in this act were the remainder of all they could recover of stocks that had been inactive over a number of years.
- 05/06 January 2010 – The UDA carries out a major act of decommissioning conducted in the presence of independent witnesses. The leadership states that the arms decommissioned include the remainder of those under its control.
- 01 February 2010 – The INLA carries out a second act of decommissioning in front of independent witnesses, and their representative reports that the arms concerned were the remainder of those under the leadership's control.
- 08 February 2010 – The South East Antrim Brigade also carries out a decommissioning act of what they state is the remainder of their arms.

REFLECTIONS ON THE PROCESS

36. **Mandate.** Reflecting on the mandate given us by the two Governments, we believe that the direction in the original legislation and in subsequent government documents, as well as the parameters within which we were required to operate, were valid, necessary and appropriate to the circumstance. Nonetheless, the nature of that direction made the task of implementing the decommissioning mandate difficult in one respect. While the two Decommissioning Acts of 1997 were explicit and detailed, and while the Schemes and Regulations gave us the necessary authority and flexibility to carry out our task, the fact that several issues were left to our judgement was a concern to some, who would have preferred to see more specificity in the direction and more transparency in its execution.

37. If the Governments had been specific as to what methods had to be used to carry out decommissioning – in what circumstances, by which date and whether or not in the public eye – our task would have been simpler. But we believe it is unlikely that it would have been successful. We believe that the flexibility given us to negotiate and agree with each of the paramilitary groups the terms and method of decommissioning – while ensuring that they met the requirements of the legislation and did not demonstrate victory or defeat – was fundamental to decommissioning taking place at all.

38. **Transparency.** It was evident to us, as it had been to the International Body in 1996, that the clear wish of those who had suffered at the hands of paramilitary groups during the period of the 'Troubles' – and indeed, other members of the public and the political parties as well – would be to see

physical evidence that those same paramilitary groups had put aside their arms and foresworn violence. The manner in which the LVF conducted its first (and last) decommissioning event in 1998, with cameras and a media pool present, demonstrated the public's satisfaction at seeing paramilitary arms actually being put beyond use. In spite of our pointing out the negative consequences of a lack of transparency, all the other paramilitary groups opted to carry out their arms decommissioning in private, with only members of the Commission and in some cases EOD technicians and/or independent witnesses present. As a result, public expectations in this regard were not met. While this situation undoubtedly caused concern to some, we believe that our acceding to a paramilitary group's decision in this matter was necessary, if decommissioning was to take place.

39. **Trust.** The establishment of trust was another factor in extending the time for decommissioning to begin. As already mentioned, other than the UVF/RHC in 1997 and the LVF in 1998, paramilitary groups did not name representatives to deal with the Commission until late in 1999. Then, in addition to the paramilitary groups' other concerns, it took time to establish a sufficient level of trust between their representatives and the Commission before the former were prepared to recommend to their membership that decommissioning should happen. The basis of this trust involved each side believing that the other would do what they said they would do, and that each would always act in good faith. Some might question the concept of placing trust in individuals who represent proscribed organizations, but we found that creating trust was an essential part of our task and it proved to be fundamental to the execution of the mandate.

40. **Quantity of Arms.** This report has already made reference to the difficulty of knowing exactly the number and quantity or type of arms held by each of the paramilitary groups we dealt with – and consequently our inability to declare definitively that decommissioning has been totally completed by those groups. The reasons the paramilitary groups could not be definitive over the completeness of their arms decommissioning has also already been referred to. But we believe – partly based on the quantities we dealt with, bearing in mind some estimates; partly on the manner in which ammunition was delivered to us (frequently in containers with a wide variety of mixed calibers and different natures that reflected the results of collection from a number of different sites or individuals); and partly on our requiring the representatives to affirm that the quantities we dealt with constituted all that the group had or that was under the control of its leadership – that decommissioning, as conducted, was as complete as it could be.

LESSONS LEARNED

41. There were a number of factors not obvious to us at the outset of our involvement that are clearer now that it is at an end. These are perhaps self-evident but we repeat them as lessons learned.

42. The need for dialogue is paramount as well as the need to be impartial. The organizations we dealt with, however abhorrent they may be to their opponents and to the families and friends of their victims, each approached the process out of a desire to put an end to violence. Their wish to do so deserved respect as well as an understanding that the condition on which they based their willingness to negotiate was that political measures would be put in place to address their concerns. In that regard, and as mentioned earlier, the need to develop trust between us and the paramilitary groups we were dealing with was crucial. If either had suspected the other of harbouring resentment or of insincerity, the discussions would have gone nowhere.

43. Also as mentioned, when it became clear that decommissioning would not be rushed, and that it would indeed be tied to progress being made in the political arena, patience became a necessity. Both the Commission and the paramilitary groups were criticized for lack of progress, but it was essential that our discussions continued – or when broken off, that they were re-opened as soon as possible.

44. We found our liaison with the security forces in both jurisdictions to be essential to our operation. We could understand if members of the security forces might have been resentful of outsiders like ourselves being involved in issues that were rightfully their professional purview. As it was, we were given every courtesy and assistance by members of all the security organizations we dealt with, each of which seemed eager for us to succeed and anxious to do what they could to help us.

45. It was also essential that we had easy access to, and a good relationship with policy and operational officials of both Governments. Since these were the organizations from which we received our mandate and to which we reported, saying this may seem to be stating the obvious. Nonetheless, the officials in the Secretary of State's office and the Department of Justice to whom we reported, were always ready to receive us and to listen to any concerns we might have. Such an open and constant working relationship is essential to an organization like ours being able to operate effectively.

46. Our relationship with the Northern Ireland political parties was important to us, particularly in the early months of our operation. The advice we received about each party's thinking on decommissioning – during the period when we were reporting to the Decommissioning Sub-Committee of the Plenary Session – was helpful to us in formulating our approach to the task of making recommendations to the Governments on methodology. Our subsequent meetings with individual parties, prior to the Assembly going into full operation, were equally helpful. We benefited from hearing their views, particularly as they reflected the views of the people of Northern Ireland, and even when we received criticism, we used that to examine how we were executing our role.

47. The issue of decommissioning constituted a high-profile part of the peace process and it attracted prolonged and close international interest, so it was important that the Commission had a good relationship with the media. The public was understandably anxious to hear what we were doing and the media was always ready to meet that need; but equally, the nature of our work did not benefit from constant publicity. Indeed, those we dealt with were not anxious to have our discussions and our subsequent engagements open to the public. Members of the media in both the United Kingdom and Ireland exercised a helpful restraint in dealing with us and we are grateful to them for their forbearance.

48. The need for the potentially contrasting qualities of perseverance and flexibility became apparent in our discussions with the paramilitary representatives. Perseverance in that we were required to insist on holding to the basic precepts of our mandate (arms being rendered permanently inaccessible or permanently unusable in a safe and verifiable manner) and yet at the same time exercising the flexibility necessary to develop measures that met both our and the representatives' concerns.

49. At the risk of departing from the purely decommissioning aspects of our role and the lessons learnt from it, there are several elemental principles emanating from the overall conflict-resolution process in Northern Ireland – of which decommissioning was a significant part – that we believe might usefully be applied to other ethnic or sectarian-related conflicts. We found that a number of these principles had an impact on what we were attempting to do in executing our mandate and we offer them here accordingly:

- a. We believe there has to be a desire for a genuine peace agreement among the participants in the process – both those who are armed and unarmed. Leaders and supporters on both sides should accept that peace is preferable to continuing violence. Without acceptance of this point, any cease-fire agreement becomes tactical and subject to potential collapse by one side or the other for short-term advantage. When that

happens, the political arrangements constructed on the basis of that cease-fire collapse also;

- b. We believe there is likely to be no lasting cease-fire until key leaders and significant numbers of supporters on both sides accept that while the opposition can perhaps be fought to a standstill, it cannot ultimately be permanently eradicated – at least, not without measures being taken that are unthinkable in a free and democratic society. Some will hold firmly to the idea that if the armed security forces are unleashed, they can defeat the opposition once and for all. But the price of unleashing armed security forces is high in political and moral terms. While guns may be eliminated by force, ideas cannot be. A constructive solution is more likely to be found through negotiation and compromise, which can lead to the realisation that illegal arms are both unacceptable and unnecessary;
- c. It seems to us that peace in Northern Ireland inherently involves accepting what is referred to here as *parity of esteem*. It means accepting that the other side has an absolute right to equal protection under the rule of law. It also means that however reprehensible some acts are that were committed in the past, at some point a line needs to be drawn under them – never to forget, but to be able to move on. For many, and particularly for those who have suffered loss or grievous injury in the past, accepting this conclusion may be very difficult. For some it may be impossible and it may even take generations – but it is, we believe, a worthwhile goal;
- d. We believe that political, community and religious leaders need to say convincingly that behaviour fostering social division is unacceptable. People with influence in society should consistently make the case that peace and civility are preferable to continuing strife, no matter what grievances are held. An expression we have frequently heard in Northern Ireland refers to this situation as the *decommissioning of mindsets*. It requires leaders at all levels to accept the difficult task of telling their supporters that some previously-held convictions may no longer be tenable. We feel they should explain that the time has come to look forward, not backward. We understand that doing so takes courage and commitment;
- e. Name-calling – the use of pejoratives like “terrorist” – or the labelling of opponents – may seem justifiable, but we believe it is counter-productive to progress and it increases the influence of those opposed to compromise. Moreover, until each side is willing to listen to what the other has to say, neither will understand the extent to which there is justification for the amends sought. And if one side does listen to what the other has to say, it is easier to demand that the other listen in return;
- f. We believe it is unhelpful to refuse to recognise opponents as legitimate negotiating partners. Face-to-face discussion, we feel, is essential to successful negotiation. The longer discussion is put off the longer it will take to get to the core of the underlying differences and to an exploration of where mutually acceptable compromise may lie. We think that, difficult as it may be, proponents in negotiations should be prepared early on to accept the idea that their opponents should be treated as political equals;
- g. We believe it is not helpful to demand an opponent to admit to wrongdoing. As Reference A noted, *The decommissioning process should suggest neither victory nor defeat*, and we believe this principle applies to other negotiations. It may be extremely tempting to try to arrange an outcome that can be construed as a victory over the other

side or to have decisively won the debate. But we believe that doing so will only harden an opponents' resolve not to compromise. One can negotiate compromise, but not contrition;

- h. It is our contention that extremists on either side should not be allowed to derail negotiations. Those at the fringes, the irreconcilables, should not be permitted to hijack any peace process. In the same vein we feel that political leaders should not walk away from the table when extremists commit atrocities, whose aim is designed to derail negotiations. It may be necessary to suspend the talks for a period, but some contacts should always be kept open. There will be some whose sense of injustice or indignation over the other sides' arguments is so extreme that any compromise is seen only as betrayal or treachery, and they may do whatever they can to stop the process going forward. Leaders should warn their supporters in advance that such behaviour is possible and stress the need not to react to it; and
- i. Finally, it may be the case that some difficult issues can usefully be addressed by using organizations or individuals drawn from outside. But we think it should be made clear that those individuals or bodies are simply the instruments to help reach a satisfactory conclusion to the dispute – and that a conclusion that will satisfy the majority can only be reached by the participants themselves.

FUTURE ARMS DECOMMISSIONING

50. We have been asked our views on future arms decommissioning in Northern Ireland, which we take to include dealing with the arms of currently active paramilitary groups as well as the disposal of arms belonging to those groups which have already decommissioned, but some of whose misplaced arms may subsequently come to light.

51. One response is that the Independent International Commission on Decommissioning is a body enacted by law in both the United Kingdom and Ireland, and while its mandate ceased at the end of February 2010, it can be brought back into being again whenever necessary under new legislation. Thus with the agreement of both Governments, a Commission could be reconstituted with a new mandate at any time. It could then deal both with active paramilitary groups that declare ceasefires and that wish to disarm, as well as with any arms that subsequently come to light within other organizations seeking to dispose of them without penalty.

52. It may be that a different approach needs to be taken in dealing with the arms of groups that are not now on ceasefire, and the new discovery of arms belonging to those who have already decommissioned.

53. **Arms Newly Discovered.** As already mentioned, a small number of arms belonging to groups which have already decommissioned may still come to light. This situation could arise against the background set out in paragraph 25. It would seem to us that in such an event consideration could be given to the terms of the current legislation preventing the forensic testing of arms being continued. The newly discovered arms could be turned over to individuals approved by the paramilitary group concerned and empowered by the respective Government to receive and deal with them. Such individuals may or may not be foreign nationals and may or may not include members of the security forces. Whoever is chosen, they could be mandated to arrange decommissioning in a manner consistent with the current legislation, that is, to render arms permanently inaccessible or permanently unusable.

54. **Decommissioning the Arms of Active Groups.** The legislation in References B and C was made at a time when a political solution to the troubles in Northern Ireland had not yet been reached. Decommissioning was called for as progress was made in the political discussions, and, subsequent to the approval of the Good Friday/Belfast Agreement, it was expected to take place as the terms of that Agreement were implemented. That situation is in the past. The paramilitary groups that declared ceasefires to allow politics to address their concerns have now decommissioned their arms, there now being in place political structures to address those concerns.

55. If and when paramilitary groups that are currently active decide to declare ceasefires and decommission their arms, it is likely they will wish to be treated in the same way as groups that decommissioned theirs earlier. They should be given that opportunity and a Commission should be re-enacted and mandated to allow that. We would suggest that a specific and shortened period of time be given for decommissioning, since the question of political progress is no longer a factor. We would also suggest that if the question of mandate-extension does become a factor, a simpler process might be considered.

56. Looking back on the experience of earlier decommissioning, we would emphasize the importance of reintegrating into society the members of paramilitary groups who voluntarily cease their paramilitary activities. Concern over this issue, and its effect on some communities, was one reason decommissioning was delayed earlier, and it may be an issue with members of groups currently active. The reintegration into society of those previously involved in conflict is accepted by the United Nations as an integral part of conflict-resolution and we believe it applies to the Northern Ireland conflict as well.

CONCLUSION

57. The leadership of the IRA, the UVF/RHC, the UDA, the South East Antrim group of the UDA, the OIRA, the INLA and the Shoukri paramilitary element, have all declared that the arms they decommissioned constituted all they had under their control. The Commission accepts their declaration. However it seems inevitable that some paramilitary arms remain un-decommissioned, either through loss or remaining in the hands of those who have not acceded to their leadership's direction, and it is unclear if all of the LVF's arms (if that group still exists as an organization) are decommissioned. While we recognize that this situation is unsatisfactory, it is important to note that each of the paramilitary organizations we dealt with (the LVF excepted) has stated that for them the war is over and that they have undertaken to pursue their goals by political and democratic means exclusively.

58. Earlier reference to dissident paramilitary groups still being active raises an area where the Commission has had no success. During our involvement in the process we have examined, sometimes in conjunction with some of the paramilitary groups with which we were in contact, the possibility of opening up discussions with groups such as the Continuity IRA and the Real IRA. We have also made public our readiness to open such discussions. We were unsuccessful in doing so and the decommissioning of the arms of those organizations remains outstanding.

59. In closing its operation, the members of the Commission wish to thank all who co-operated with us for their support and assistance throughout the lengthy period we have been entrusted with this challenging mission.

Brigadier Tauno Nieminen

General John de Chastelain

Andrew D. Sens

- ANNEXES
- A. Report of the International Body 22 January 1996
 - B. The Northern Ireland Arms Decommissioning Act 1997 (UK)
 - C. The Northern Ireland Arms Decommissioning Act 1997 (Ireland)
 - D. Agreement between the Government of Ireland and the Government of the United Kingdom Establishing the Independent International Commission on Decommissioning, 26 August 1997
 - E. Decommissioning Scheme, Northern Ireland Office, 29 June 1998
 - F. Decommissioning Regulations, Government of Ireland, 29 June 1998
 - G. Decommissioning Scheme, Northern Ireland Office, 2 August 2001
 - H. Decommissioning Regulations, Government of Ireland, 3 August 2001
 - I. IICD Proposal to the Governments for a Decommissioning Scheme I, 15 January 1998.
 - J. IICD Proposal to the Governments for a Decommissioning Scheme II, 1 January 1998.
 - K. IICD Reports to the Governments, 21 November 1997 to 25 February 2010.

Please note that the annexes to this report are available on the NIO website www.nio.gov.uk

INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING

Brigadier Tauno Nieminen

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25 February 2010

REPORT OF THE INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING

To: Rt. Hon. Shaun Woodward, MP
Secretary of State for Northern Ireland
Belfast

To: Mr Dermot Ahern, T.D.
Minister for Justice, Equality and Law Reform
Dublin

Introduction

1. This report covers the period since our last written report on 4 September 2009 and details the decommissioning of paramilitary arms conducted by us during that period.

Ulster Defence Association

2. In January 2010 we carried out a major decommissioning event with the Ulster Defence Association. This event was further to one executed with the UDA in June 2009 and was conducted in the presence of witnesses provided by the UDA. Substantial quantities of arms and ammunition were decommissioned during the event as well as some explosives and explosive devices. The leadership of the UDA has informed us that these arms constitute all the arms under their control.

Official Irish Republican Army

3. In October 2009 and in January 2010 we carried out two events in which a quantity of arms and ammunition belonging to the OIRA were decommissioned. The events were also witnessed by individuals nominated by the OIRA. The OIRA representatives informed us that the arms decommissioned were all they could recover of stocks that have been inactive over a number of years.

Irish National Liberation Army

4. In December 2009 and February 2010 we carried out events in which quantities of arms and ammunition as well as some explosives and explosive devices belonging to the INLA were decommissioned. These events were facilitated through intermediaries chosen by the INLA, who also

witnessed the decommissioning events. The INLA representatives informed us that these arms were all they had under their control.

UDA South East Antrim Group

5. In February 2010 we carried out an event in which weapons, ammunition, explosives and explosive devices belonging to the UDA South East Antrim Group were decommissioned. This event was further to other events conducted in October 2007 and January and May 2009. The UDA representatives have informed us that these arms constitute the final amount under the Group's control.

Shoukri Paramilitary Element

6. In December 2009 we carried out an event in which some arms, ammunition and explosive devices belonging to the Shoukri paramilitary element were decommissioned. This event followed two previous events in which a small number of arms and ammunition were also decommissioned. The Shoukri element has stated that the arms decommissioned were all it had under its control.

Conclusion

7. At the direction of both governments the Commission's mandate has been terminated with effect 9 February 2010 in the British jurisdiction and 25 February 2010 in the jurisdiction of the Republic of Ireland. Accordingly this is the last operational report we will submit to the two governments.

8. We will now review with the governments the measures they wish us to take to close our offices in Belfast and Dublin and to complete the final report they require from us prior to our standing down.

Brigadier Tauno Nieminen

General John de Chastelain

Andrew D. Sens

INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING

General John de Chastelain

Brigadier-General Tauno Nieminen

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STATEMENT

8 February 2010

On INLA Decommissioning

“The IICD can confirm that it has conducted events in which quantities of firearms, ammunition, explosives and explosive devices belonging to the INLA have been decommissioned. The events were attended by witnesses chosen by the INLA. The INLA representatives have informed us that the arms decommissioned constitute all those under the control of the INLA leadership.”

End of statement

INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING

General John de Chastelain

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STATEMENT

6 January 2009

“The IICD confirms that, having started the decommissioning process with the Ulster Defence Association last June, we have now conducted a major act of decommissioning in which arms, ammunition, explosives and explosive devices belonging to the Ulster Defence Association have been destroyed within the terms of our mandate.

The leadership of the Ulster Defence Association has informed us that these armaments constitute the totality of those under their control.

The IICD reminds paramilitary organizations which may still have arms in their possession that we have until the 9th of February this year to complete our mandate and we urge them to contact us soon to that effect.”

End of statement

INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING

Brigadier Tauno Nieminen

General John de Chastelain

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04 September 2009

REPORT OF THE INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING

To: Rt. Hon. Shaun Woodward, MP
Secretary of State for Northern Ireland
Belfast

To: Mr Dermot Ahern, T.D.
Minister for Justice, Equality and Law Reform
Dublin

Introduction

1. In renewing the Commission's mandate for a final year, both governments asked the Commission to produce a report in August on progress made in decommissioning loyalist paramilitary arms.

Ulster Volunteer Force/Red Hand Commando

2. In verbal reports to both governments in June we said that we had overseen a decommissioning event in which substantial quantities of firearms, ammunition, explosives and explosive devices belonging to the Ulster Volunteer Force and the Red Hand Commando had been decommissioned.

3. The UVF and RHC representatives told us that some of their arms had been lost over the years through seizure by the security services, deterioration or damage, or the death of those responsible for them. They said that the arms decommissioned under our supervision in June comprised all that was under the control of both organizations.

Ulster Defence Association

4. In June 2009 we also reported to both governments that we had overseen an act in which a quantity of weapons belonging to the Ulster Defence Association had been decommissioned. We reported that representatives of the UDA told us this was the first in a series of acts in which they would decommission the remainder of their arms before the expiration of the Commission's mandate. They also

informed us that the weapons decommissioned in that event included some belonging to each of the five UDA brigades.

5. Since June we have continued to meet with UDA representatives to plan further decommissioning events and to encourage the group to complete the task as soon as possible. Given recent speculation on a possible split within the UDA, and the suggestion that the Londonderry/North Antrim brigade had refused – or could not get agreement – to decommission its arms, we met this week with the leaders of all five brigades together. They told us that there was no difference of opinion among them on decommissioning and that each of them was committed to completing the process within the time remaining to the Commission. To that end we will continue to meet with the representatives in the coming months.

UDA South East Antrim Group

6. Over the past number of months we have overseen two events in which some of the UDA South East Antrim group's weapons, ammunition, explosives and explosives devices were decommissioned. The group's representatives have committed to decommission the remainder of their arms before the Commission's mandate ends and we continue to urge them to do this as soon as possible.

Conclusion

7. In conclusion we feel that substantial practical progress has been made on decommissioning Loyalist paramilitary arms. We believe we have completed the decommissioning of UVF/RHC arms and we have been given a commitment by representatives of the UDA and the UDA South East Antrim group that they will complete the decommissioning of their arms within the timeframe of the Commission's current and final mandate.

8. We will continue to keep the two governments advised on progress.

Brigadier Tauno Nieminen

General John de Chastelain

Andrew D. Sens

INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING

Brigadier Tauno Nieminen

General John de Chastelain

Andrew D. Sens

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REPORT OF THE INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING

To:

The Rt. Hon. Peter Hain, MP
Secretary of State for Northern Ireland
BELFAST

To:

Mr. Michael McDowell, TD
Minister for Justice, Equality and Law Reform
DUBLIN

1. Since we reported to you last September, we have continued in our efforts to execute our remit. We have concentrated on the Loyalist paramilitary groups and attempted to engage with them in the pursuit of our mandate. We also wish to advise you of actions we have taken regarding security assessments recently received concerning IRA arms.
2. We have now held several meetings with the UPRG, including some in which a UDA representative participated. While these have not led to firm decommissioning proposals, we are advised that the UDA is prepared to address the issue of arms in the context of a satisfactory consideration by the British government of its community's socio-economic concerns.
3. While the LVF has not resumed formal contact with us, it has authorized informal discussions with an intermediary and we have held a number of meetings with him. We are aware of recent media reports in which the LVF has signalled its intention to stand down its activities. While we have no indication how such a stand-down would involve the disposal of LVF arms, we have emphasized that their decommissioning must take place under our supervision. We are led to understand that the LVF wishes to receive community-related assurances from the British government before any action on its arms proceeds.
4. The UVF has not resumed formal contact with us but we will continue in our attempts to re-open this channel in the coming months.
5. We are aware of several media reports since our September announcement suggesting that the IRA may still hold some arms. Last week we were informed by security sources in Northern Ireland that they had intelligence to the effect that some individuals and groups within the IRA have retained a range of arms including handguns. There was no indication that the quantities of arms involved were substantial. We were also told there is no suggestion these arms (purportedly kept for personal

protection and area defence) have been retained with the approval of the IRA leadership or as part of any wider strategy to return to violence.

6. If substantiated, this assessment would be at variance with the statement we made last September that we believed all IRA arms had been decommissioned commensurate with our remit. Accordingly, we undertook to examine whether, in light of the assessment, we were misinformed or had made a misjudgement in September.

7. Our statement then that all IRA arms had been decommissioned was qualified – as we said at the time – by the representative's assurance that while the IRA had gathered for decommissioning all the arms under its control, and while these arms had subsequently been put beyond use under our supervision, it could not guarantee that a small number might not have gone astray over the years as individual custodians died or the locations of some caches were lost.

8. Over the past week we have discussed the intelligence assessment with senior officers in the Garda Síochána. Intelligence available to the Garda at the time of decommissioning last year indicated that extensive efforts had been made by the IRA to locate and gather weapons, which, in turn, were put beyond use in the process overseen by us. Further, the Garda informed us that what they regard as reliable sources in relation to the IRA and its weaponry, have produced no intelligence suggesting any arms have been retained.

9. In our first meeting last week the IRA representative confirmed that the leadership remains committed to its statement of 28 July, in which it announced an end to the armed campaign and ordered all IRA units to dump their arms. He re-iterated that all the arms that were dumped following that statement were then collected and put beyond use in September under our supervision. He assured us that no IRA arms had been retained or placed in long term hides.

10. In a meeting later in the week the representative told us that following our earlier discussion, the IRA leadership questioned each of their commanders about the intelligence assessment. These have confirmed that all the arms under their control were decommissioned in September, as we stated.

11. We are re-assured by the fact that none of the various intelligence assessments suggest the IRA leadership is moving away from its July 28 commitments. We conclude that in the absence of evidence to the contrary our 26 September assessment regarding IRA arms remains correct.

12. We have informed the Independent Monitoring Commission of the substance of this report so they are kept aware of developments in our area of responsibility.

Tauno Nieminen

John de Castelain

Andrew Sens

19 January 2006

Statement by the Independent International Commission on Decommissioning (IICD), 21 October 2003

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**STATEMENT BY THE
INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING
(IICD)
21 October 2003**

No 'official' report was issued by the IICD on 21 October 2003. The following is (a draft version) of a statement made by General John de Chastelain at a press conference at Hillsborough, County Down.

"The commission has witnessed a third event in which IRA weapons are put beyond use in accordance with the government scheme and regulations.

The arms comprise light, medium and heavy ordnance and associated munitions.

They include automatic weapons, ammunition, explosives and explosive material.

The quantity of weapons involved was larger than the quantity put beyond use in the previous event.

I do want to make the point - and that is why we have indicated this time - that the amount of arms put beyond use was larger - I would say considerably larger - than the previous event."

Andrew D. Sens, Member of the IICD, added:

"The material put beyond use this morning could have caused death or destruction on a huge scale had it been put to use."

Hillsborough, 21 October 2003

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Report of the Independent International Commission on Decommissioning (IICD), 22 April 2002

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**REPORT OF THE
INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING
(IICD)
8 April 2002**

To: The Rt Hon. John Reid, MP Secretary of State for Northern Ireland, Belfast	To: Mr. John O'Donoghue, TD, Minister of Justice, Equality and Law Reform, Dublin
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1. We wish to inform you that we have witnessed an event in which the IRA leadership has put a varied and substantial quantity of ammunition, arms and explosive material beyond use. In accordance with the Governments' Scheme and Regulations, we have made an inventory of the arms concerned, which we will provide to the two governments when our task is completed.
2. As before, we have agreed to the IRA's condition of confidentiality regarding details of this event, as provided for in the same Scheme and Regulations.
3. We will continue our discussions with the IRA representative in the pursuit of our remit. We will also continue our discussions with the loyalist paramilitary groups.

Signed: Tauno Nieminen John de Chastelain Andrew D. Sens

Belfast, 8 April 2002

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Statement by the Independent International Commission on Decommissioning (IICD), 23 October 2001

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STATEMENT BY THE INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING (IICD) 23 October 2001

Table with 2 columns: To: The Rt Hon. John Reid, MP Secretary of State for Northern Ireland, Belfast; To: Mr. John O'Donoghue, TD, Minister of Justice, Equality and Law Reform, Dublin

- 1. On August 6 2001, the Commission reported that agreement had been reached with the IRA on a method to put IRA arms completely and verifiably beyond use. This would be done in such a way as to involve no risk to the public and avoid the possibility of misappropriation by others.
2. We have now witnessed an event - which we regard as significant - in which the IRA has put a quantity of arms completely beyond use. The material in question includes arms, ammunition and explosives.
3. We are satisfied that the arms in question have been dealt with in accordance with the scheme and regulations. We are also satisfied that it would not further the process of putting all arms beyond use were we to provide further details of this event.
4. We will continue our contact with the IRA representative in the pursuit of our mandate.

Signed: Tauno Nieminen John de Chastelain Andrew D. Sens

Belfast, 23 October 2001

Table with 2 columns: Dublin Office (Dublin Castle, Block M, Ship Street, DUBLIN 2, Tel No: 00 353 (0)1 4780111, Fax No: 00 353 (0)1 4780600); Belfast Office (Rosepark House, Upper Newtownards Road, BELFAST, BT4 3NX, Tel No: 00 44 (0)28 9048 8600, Fax No: 00 44 (0)28 9048 8601)

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Statement by the Independent International Commission on Decommissioning (IICD), 6 August 2001

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STATEMENT BY THE INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING (IICD) 6 August 2001

Table with 2 columns: To: The Rt Hon. John Reid, MP Secretary of State for Northern Ireland, Belfast; To: Mr. John O'Donoghue, TD, Minister of Justice, Equality and Law Reform, Dublin

"In a recent meeting with the Commission, the IRA representative proposed a method for putting IRA arms completely and verifiably beyond use.

"We are satisfied that this proposal meets the Commission's remit in accordance with the Governments' scheme and regulations.

"Based on our discussions with the IRA representative, we believe that this proposal initiates a process that will put IRA arms completely and verifiably beyond use."

Signed: Tauno Nieminen John de Chastelain Andrew D. Sens

Belfast, 6 August 2001

Table with 2 columns: Dublin Office (Dublin Castle, Block M, Ship Street, DUBLIN 2, Tel No: 00 353 (0)1 4780111, Fax No: 00 353 (0)1 4780600); Belfast Office (Rosepark House, Upper Newtownards Road, BELFAST, BT4 3NX, Tel No: 00 44 (0)28 9048 8600, Fax No: 00 44 (0)28 9048 8601)

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**Report of the Independent International Commission on
Decommissioning (IICD), 30 June 2001**

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**REPORT OF THE
INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING
(IICD)
30 June 2001**

To: The Rt Hon. John Reid, MP Secretary of State for Northern Ireland, Belfast	To: Mr. John O'Donoghue, TD, Minister of Justice, Equality and Law Reform, Dublin
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INTRODUCTION

1. On 05 May 2000 the two Governments said the remaining steps necessary to secure full implementation of the Agreement could be achieved by June 2001. Decommissioning of paramilitary arms was one of the remaining steps and we submit this report accordingly.

2. During the past year the UVF and UFF representatives gave us general agreement on methods of decommissioning and supporting issues, although the UFF representatives recently qualified their continuing discussion of the subject with us. Since the IRA re-opened engagement with us in March 2001, we focussed on ascertaining details of the IRA's commitment to put its arms beyond use.

3. The commitments given us to date notwithstanding, we must report that no decommissioning by the IRA, the UVF and the UFF has yet started, although each of these groups has re-affirmed the circumstances under which they might do so.

DISCUSSIONS WITH THE IRA REPRESENTATIVE

4. Since March, we have held a number of lengthy meetings with the IRA representative, most recently within the past week. During each of the meetings we have pressed for answers to three questions:

- a. The IRA's commitment to put its arms beyond use;
- b. The method it will use and whether it meets our remit to verify that arms are rendered permanently inaccessible or permanently unusable; and
- c. When the process of putting arms beyond use will begin.

5. In each of our meetings we have been assured of the IRA's commitment to put its arms beyond use, completely and verifiably, but only in the context of its statement of 06 May 2000. Taken in conjunction with the continued maintenance of the July 1997 ceasefire, and the opening of some IRA arms dumps to inspections by the International Inspectors, we believe that this conditional commitment is made in good faith.

6. We have, however, been unable to ascertain how the IRA will put its arms beyond use, except for the assurance that it will be complete and verifiable. The IRA has taken note of our need for this information, but until we know what method will be used, we cannot judge if it meets our remit. We should record that the representative has said he wishes to continue to engage with us on issues related to our remit as the political process continues.

7. We should also note that in May 2000 the Governments asked us to consider decommissioning methods other than the two already approved. We have done so, and we made clear to the IRA representative that we would welcome suggestions in this regard.

DISCUSSIONS WITH THE UVF REPRESENTATIVE

8. We have had a number of discussions with the UVF representative, most recently this week. He confirms that the statements he made earlier on decommissioning methods and supporting issues remain in effect; but he re-iterates that the UVF will not consider decommissioning before they know the IRA's intentions and hear their declaration that the war is over.

DISCUSSIONS WITH THE UFF REPRESENTATIVES

9. Similarly we have had a number of discussions with the UFF representatives, most recently this week. At this most recent meeting, while the representatives did not withdraw their earlier statements on decommissioning methods and supporting issues, they told us it would be difficult to discuss decommissioning further with us "while members of the UFF were continuing to be interned."

CONCLUSION

10. We have been unable to meet either of the decommissioning target dates called for by the Agreement or by the Governments: respectively, 22 May 2000 and June 2001. Some people have said they believe our inability to engineer a start to decommissioning has called into question our usefulness to the process, and suggest we now withdraw from it. Others have urged us to remain engaged and to continue to press paramilitary groups to begin decommissioning. We have given both these views careful consideration.

11. Given the conditions the IRA, the UVF and the UFF say they require before they will put their arms beyond use, we believe we cannot influence that activity by making demands or by setting deadlines. But we will continue to do what we can to implement our mandate through continuing contact and discussion with each of the three paramilitary groups, insisting that the objectives of the legislation calling for arms to be rendered permanently inaccessible or permanently unusable are respected. We will do so mindful that this contentious issue must be resolved as soon as possible.

Signed: Tauno Nieminen John de Chastelain Andrew D. Sens

Belfast, 30 June 2001

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**STATEMENT BY THE
INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING
(IICD)
30 May 2001**

To: The Rt Hon. John Reid, MP Secretary of State for Northern Ireland, Belfast	To: Mr. John O'Donoghue, TD, Minister of Justice, Equality and Law Reform, Dublin
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1. We have been advised by the Inspectors that they have carried out a third inspection of IRA arms. A copy of their [report](#) is attached.

2. Since our reported meeting in March with the IRA representative, we have continued to engage with him in the pursuit of our mandate.

Signed: Tauno Nieminen John de Chastelain Andrew D. Sens

Belfast, 30 May 2001

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REPORT OF THE INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING (IICD) 22 March 2001

To: The Rt Hon. John Reid, MP Secretary of State for Northern Ireland, Belfast	To: Mr. John O'Donoghue, TD, Minister of Justice, Equality and Law Reform, Dublin
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1. Since our 22 December 2000 report to the Governments there has been no actual decommissioning, but events of the past few weeks lead us to believe that progress on it can be made. This report will comment on those events.
2. Meetings in recent weeks with representatives of the UVF and the UFF confirmed their willingness to consider decommissioning their arms, and their general agreement on methods and related supporting issues. Both groups continue to affirm that they will not move on decommissioning before the IRA does so.
3. On 8 March the IRA published a statement in which they stated in part: "...the IRA leadership has decided to enter into further discussions with the IICD. This will be on the basis of the IRA leadership's commitment to resolving the issues contained in our statement of May 6th 2000, and on no other basis." In a telephone call later the same day, the IRA renewed contact with the Commission.
4. Subsequently a meeting was held between the Commission and the IRA representative. At that meeting we reviewed developments since our last meeting and established a basis for further discussions. We welcomed the re-engagement with the IRA representative and consider it to be in good faith. We will build on it at future such meetings which we expect will occur soon.
5. We will keep the Governments advised of progress as it occurs.

Signed: Tauno Nieminen John de Chastelain Andrew D. Sens

Belfast, 22 March 2001

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REPORT OF THE INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING (IICD)

22 December 2000

To: The Rt. Hon. Peter Mandelson, MP Secretary of State for Northern Ireland, Belfast	To: Mr. John O'Donoghue, TD, Minister of Justice, Equality and Law Reform, Dublin
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1. This report has been delayed until just before the Christmas break in the knowledge that considerable efforts are ongoing to resolve the impasse over decommissioning. Should there be a change in the current situation we will issue a further report.
2. In our 26 October report we stated we had not made progress on actual decommissioning up to that time. That remains the case to date.
3. Since the last report we have continued to meet with political parties. We have also engaged with the UVF and UFF representatives and we have urged re-engagement by the IRA representative. The UVF representatives have met with us and confirmed the commitment to decommissioning they previously gave us. They have warned that in their opinion dissident activity has made decommissioning harder to achieve, but they stand by their agreement on decommissioning methods and supporting issues. Recent meetings of the UFF representatives have confirmed to us their previously-given commitments on decommissioning.
4. We welcome the end of the loyalist feud and believe that this development, coupled with re-engagement with us by the IRA representative, would mark a positive step forward on decommissioning.
5. In their public statement of 5 December the IRA re-confirmed their readiness "to initiate a process that would completely and verifiably put IRA arms beyond use and to do so in a way to avoid risk to the public, misappropriation by others and ensure maximum public confidence". We welcome that commitment as helpful, as we do their statement that "we have not broken off contact with the IICD and we remain committed to discussions with them on the basis we have set out".
6. In May the Governments invited the Commission to examine, with paramilitary group representatives, further proposals for decommissioning schemes beyond the two approved by them. We already have agreement in principle on schemes with the UVF and UFF. We are anxious to explore with the IRA representative their proposal to put arms beyond use and our role in that process.
7. The Governments' 5 May statement indicated that they "now believe that the remaining steps necessary to secure full implementation of the Agreement can be achieved by June 2001, and commit themselves to that goal". Again the Commission remains prepared to state, if necessary, when we believe decommissioning must start and how it must proceed if we are to fulfil our mandate within the required period. We believe that sufficient time still exists for the complete decommissioning of paramilitary arms by June 2001, and that appropriate methods can be set up for that purpose.
8. We believe it is crucial that we have substantive engagement with the IRA representative as soon as possible, followed by early movement on actual decommissioning by each of the paramilitary groups, if we are to meet the Agreement's decommissioning requirements by the beginning of June.

Signed: Tauno Nieminen John de Chastelain Andrew D. Sens

Belfast, 22 December 2000

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**REPORT OF THE
INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING
(IICD)
26 October 2000**

To: The Rt. Hon. Peter Mandelson, MP Secretary of State for Northern Ireland, Belfast	To: Mr. John O'Donoghue, TD, Minister of Justice, Equality and Law Reform, Dublin
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BACKGROUND

1. On 11 February 2000 the Commission provided a written report to the two Governments in which we commented on our contacts with the IRA and loyalist representatives, and especially on the proposal made that day by the IRA to initiate a comprehensive process to put arms beyond use. On 25 June 2000 we forwarded the International Inspectors' first report on the inspection of IRA arms dumps to the Governments. A second inspection has now taken place. We also wish to bring the Governments up to date on the work of the Commission during the period since February.

SECOND INSPECTION

2. Today the Inspectors reported to the Commission that they have carried out a second inspection. They confirmed they had re-inspected the arms dumps previously seen, which held a substantial amount of military materiel, including explosives and related equipment. They also confirmed that the dumps had not been tampered with and remained secure. The Inspectors reported that, again, they had consulted with independent specialists on the technical aspects of their task.

3. A copy of that report is available here.

PERIOD FROM MARCH TO AUGUST 2000

4. On 15 February, after the suspension of the institutions, the IRA announced that: "In the light of these changed circumstances the leadership of the IRA have decided to end our engagement with the IICD. We are also withdrawing all propositions put to the IICD by our representative since November."

5. During the period from March to June, the Commission maintained contact with the UVF and UFF, as well as meeting with representatives of the political parties, the security forces and the Governments.

6. On 5 May 2000 the two Governments issued a statement in which they said they: "□ now believe that the remaining steps necessary to secure full implementation of the Agreement can be achieved by June 2001, and commit themselves to that goal." They added that: "Subject to a positive response to this statement, the British Government will bring forward the necessary order to enable the Assembly and Executive to be restored by 22 May 2000."

7. In their 5 May statement the Governments also called on the Commission: "□ to consider urgently, in consultation with representatives of the paramilitary organisations, whether there are any further proposals for decommissioning schemes which offer the Commission greater scope to proceed in more effective and satisfactory ways with the discharge of its mandate and to report. The Governments will give early consideration to any such proposals. The Commission will make further reports as necessary. Those reports will be published promptly by the two governments."

8. On 6 May 2000 the IRA released a statement in which they said in part: "We will resume contact with the IICD and enter into further discussion with the Commission on the basis of the IRA leadership's commitment to resolving the issue of arms". They also noted they would open a number of their arms dumps to International Inspectors as a confidence building measure, and that the Inspectors would report on their inspections to the Commission.

9. On 25 June the Commission informed the two Governments that the Inspectors had reported they had completed an initial inspection of a substantial number of IRA arms.

10. On the same day the IRA's representative called the Commission, formally re-opening contact, and on 26 June the IRA made public an announcement to that effect and confirming that the initial inspection of arms had taken place.

11. In late June, it was suggested to the Commission that the circumstances surrounding the marching season made it unlikely that progress would be made on decommissioning during the months of July and August. However, the Commission kept the offices in Belfast and Dublin open during these two months, with a reduced number of personnel available to respond immediately to any decommissioning initiative.

PERIOD OF SEPTEMBER-OCTOBER 2000

12. In early September the Commission renewed its efforts to meet with representatives of the three paramilitary groups. Its aim was in part to determine what the IRA meant by its intention to "initiate a process that will completely and verifiably put arms beyond use", and to assess whether such a process corresponds to the remit given the Commission by the Governments to facilitate the destruction of paramilitary arms. Separately, the Commission's aim was to ascertain the loyalist paramilitary groups' continuing intentions on decommissioning.

13. Over a period of six weeks, the Commission was unable to arrange meetings with the paramilitary representatives. Meetings with political parties elicited reasons as to why they believed meetings had not occurred. On the republican side these were attributed in part to concerns over the implementation of the Patten Report on policing, to the slow pace of demilitarisation, and to concerns over republicans wanted for questioning by the authorities. On the loyalist side they were attributed in part to the failure of the IRA to respond to the Commission in practical terms on decommissioning, as well as to internal problems associated with the ongoing loyalist feud. In some cases these opinions were made public by the political parties concerned.

14. During the six week period from the beginning of September to the middle of October, the Commission reported frequently to the governments at the officials' level. In the same period the Commission met with representatives of six different political parties, some of them several times, as well as with the Ulster Unionist Party Review Group. During these meetings the Commission responded frankly to questions concerning progress on decommissioning. Also during the period the Commission held meetings with the security forces north and south.

15. Some days ago the Commission informed political parties that it had scheduled a meeting with ministers from both Governments to take place during the week of 23 October, to give a report on progress. The Commission stressed the urgency of meeting with the paramilitary representatives before that date to enable it to make the most complete and informed report possible.

16. On 17 October the Commission met with representatives of the UFF. During the discussion they re-iterated their adherence to the terms of the Agreement, including to decommissioning. They re-affirmed their decision not to begin decommissioning their arms until the IRA started to decommission theirs, although they stood by their earlier commitment to the Commission on methods of decommissioning and supporting arrangements. They also pointed out that at present, the ongoing feud between the UFF and the UVF made decommissioning both difficult and unlikely in the short term. They agreed to maintain contact with the Commission and to inform us of any change in their position.

17. The Commission has not been able to engage with the IRA representative since the re-opening of contact in June. In their statement yesterday, the IRA said: "We have also decided to resume discussions with the IICD when we are satisfied that the peace process will be advanced by those discussions". The Commission will continue its efforts to meet with the IRA representative to determine whether "putting arms beyond use" meets the Commission's mandate for arms destruction and when that process will begin.

18. The Commission has not been able to meet with the UVF representative since June, although there have been several telephone conversations with him during September and October. The Commission will continue its attempts to meet with the representative to ascertain whether the UVF's previously-stated position on decommissioning has advanced.

CONCLUSION

19. The Commission cannot report progress on actual decommissioning during the period following the IRA's renewal of contact in June, and the UVF and UFF's earlier acceptance of methods of decommissioning and supporting issues. That noted, we welcome the Inspectors' report today and look forward to further such reports.

20. We also welcome the fact that the IRA, UVF and UFF maintain their contact with the Commission, and the IRA's reaffirmation of its commitment to resolving the issue of arms.

21. In the meantime, we will continue to concentrate our efforts on furthering our sole mandate, the decommissioning of paramilitary arms.

Signed: Tauno Nieminen John de Chastelain Andrew D. Sens

Belfast, 26 October 2000

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STATEMENT BY THE
INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING
(IICD)
25 June 2000

To: The Rt. Hon. Peter Mandelson, MP Secretary of State for Northern Ireland, Belfast	To: Mr. John O'Donoghue, TD, Minister of Justice, Equality and Law Reform, Dublin
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Gentlemen:

President Martti Ahtisaari and Mr Cyril Ramaphosa informed the Commission today that they have successfully completed an initial inspection of several IRA weapons dumps. The two inspectors report that they were shown a substantial quantity of IRA arms, including explosives.

Moreover, the inspectors have ensured that the weapons are secure and cannot be used without their becoming aware that this has happened.

Signed: Tauno Nieminen John de Chastelain Andrew D. Sens

Belfast, 25 June 2000

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REPORT OF THE INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING (IICD) 11 February 2000

To: The Rt. Hon. Peter Mandelson, MP Secretary of State for Northern Ireland, Belfast	To: Mr. John O'Donoghue, TD, Minister of Justice, Equality and Law Reform, Dublin
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1. In our report of 31 January 2000, the Commission stated that the intense negotiations were continuing and we would report any concrete result that came from them. Since then we have had several contacts with the IRA and loyalist representatives.

2. The IRA declaration of support for the process leading to a permanent peace in Ireland, the contribution made by the ceasefires and the statement that the IRA provides no threat to that process are recognised.

We believe that these are important issues of considerable significance for peace and stability in Northern Ireland and they were reflected in our 31 January report.

3. Since December 1999, the IRA has engaged frankly and helpfully with the Commission and we note their intention to continue to do so.

4. We also note the IRA assessment that the question of British forces and loyalist paramilitaries in Northern Ireland must be addressed. While the future of British troops is outside our remit, the elimination of the threat posed by the loyalist paramilitary arms is clearly within the Commission's remit.

We have been advised by loyalist representatives of their commitment to address the issue of their arms in the context of similar action taken by the IRA.

In our discussions this week with the UVF and UFF representatives, each confirmed their positions as stated in our 31 January report and the UFF representatives further engaged with us on methods of decommissioning and related support issues.

5. We welcome the IRA's belief that the "state of perpetual crisis" can be averted and that the issue of arms can be resolved.

We find particularly significant and view as valuable progress the assertion made to us by the IRA representative that the IRA will consider how to put arms and explosives beyond use, in the context of the full implementation of the Good Friday Agreement, and in the context of the removal of the causes of conflict.

6. The Commission welcomes the IRA's recognition that the issue of arms needs to be dealt with in an acceptable way and that this is a necessary objective of a genuine peace process and their statement that for those reasons they are engaged with us.

The Commission further welcomes the IRA's commitment to sustain and enhance its contribution to a durable peace and their statement that they have supported and will continue to support efforts to secure the resolution of the arms issue.

7. The representative indicated to us today the context in which the IRA will initiate a comprehensive process to put arms beyond use, in a manner as to ensure maximum public confidence.

8. The Commission believes that this commitment, on the basis described above, holds out the real prospect of an agreement which would enable it to fulfil the substance of its mandate. We will make a further report to the two Governments as appropriate.

Signed: Tauno Nieminen John de Chastelain Andrew D. Sens

Belfast, 11 February 2000

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REPORT OF THE INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING (IICD) 31 January 2000

To: The Rt. Hon. Peter Mandelson, MP Secretary of State for Northern Ireland, Belfast	To: Mr. John O'Donoghue, TD, Minister of Justice, Equality and Law Reform, Dublin
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1. In our report of 10 December, the Commission undertook to report further on decommissioning in January. This is that report. Since December, the Commission has held further discussions with representatives of the IRA, the UVF and the UFF.
2. Our previous report stated our belief that the results of the Mitchell review and the designation of IRA and UFF contacts in addition to the UVF contact already in place, gave the basis for an assessment that decommissioning will happen. While we believe that conclusion was well founded, we await further evidence to substantiate it.
3. The IRA contact has assured us of the unequivocal continuing support of his organisation for the current political process. We have been made aware of, and recognise, the difficulties facing the IRA leadership in moving on decommissioning at this time. We are also conscious that the maintenance of their ceasefire, and those of the UVF and UFF, have played and continue to play, an important part in the political advances that have been achieved to date and that are progressing. Further our contact has very recently emphasized that there is no threat to the peace process from the IRA. All of these factors are significant. But our sole task is decommissioning and to date we have received no information from the IRA as to when decommissioning will start.
4. In our most recent discussion with the UVF contact, he reminded us of the discussions he held with the Commission over a long period, including the UVF's early engagement on the issue of modalities. He has also reiterated the UVF stance that while it is prepared to consider moving on decommissioning, it will not do so until it has received an unequivocal statement from the IRA that the war is over.
5. Similarly, our most recent discussion with representatives of the UFF has confirmed their position stated during our earlier meeting, to the effect that while that group too is prepared to consider moving on decommissioning, it will not do so until it is clear that the IRA will also decommission.
6. We will continue our efforts to carry out the Commission's role in the manner and within the time-frame approved by the political parties and the two governments. However, given our understanding of the quantity of arms held by the paramilitary groups, and the dispersed nature of their locations, we believe a time will soon be reached beyond which it will be logistically impossible for us to complete our task by 22 May. We remain prepared to state, at an appropriate date, when we believe decommissioning must start and how it must proceed if our mandate is to be fulfilled within the required period. But decommissioning is a voluntary act; any schedule we produce will only be of value if those who have the arms agree to follow it.
7. The foregoing noted, intensive negotiations have taken place during the past few days. The Commission will report further to the governments in the event that ongoing negotiations lead to concrete results.
8. If it becomes clear to us that decommissioning is not to happen, the Commission will recommend to the governments that it be disbanded.

Signed: Tauno Nieminen John de Chastelain Andrew D. Sens

Belfast, 31 January 2000

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Report of the Independent International Commission on Decommissioning, 10 December 1999

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REPORT OF THE INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING 10 December 1999

To: The Rt. Hon. Peter Mandelson, MP Secretary of State for Northern Ireland, Belfast	To: Mr. John O'Donoghue, TD, Minister of Justice, Equality and Law Reform, Dublin
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1. In the 15 November assessment we prepared for Senator Mitchell, we called on paramilitary organisations to respond positively by appointing authorised representatives. We also said that we would issue a report to the governments within days of holding meetings with representatives of the paramilitary groups. This is that report. We will report further in January.

2. In the same assessment we stated our belief that "the implementation of the Agreement in all its aspects will create anew context in which the situation will be transformed." Since writing that assessment we have taken note of the much improved political atmosphere created by the establishment of the new political institutions, the renewed collective commitment of the parties, and the appointment of authorized representatives by two paramilitary groups that had not previously done so. These events provide the basis for an assessment that decommissioning will occur.

3. The Irish Republican Army (IRA) announced on 2 December that they had appointed a representative to enter into discussions with the Commission. We have held an initial meeting with that individual. The meeting was frank and useful and a further meeting has been agreed.

4. Similarly the Commission has met again with the Ulster Volunteer Force/Red Hand Commando (UVF/RHC) representative. This meeting too was frank and useful. The representative reiterated the view, provided earlier to the Commission, that "the implementation of the Good Friday Agreement in full, coupled with the acceptance from Republicans that the Agreement is the final settlement to end the constitutional conflict, are the only conditions which will facilitate the process of decommissioning weapons."

5. The Ulster Freedom Fighters (UFF) announced on 8 December that they had decided to appoint representatives to liaise directly with the Commission. Earlier today we held an initial meeting with those representatives. This meeting was helpful and we have agreed on the next meeting. The representatives impressed on us a point they made public recently, to the effect that "disarmament will only be considered in the context of the IRA having already begun to decommission its arsenal of weaponry."

6. We have noted elsewhere our belief that decommissioning cannot be imposed. But we believe that the above-mentioned achievements provide the context for the voluntary decommissioning of arms. In our 2 July report to the Governments we noted that a timetable for decommissioning is best agreed with the representatives of the paramilitary groups. We believe that still to be the case. Nonetheless, the Commission is prepared, if necessary, to state that actual decommissioning is to start within a specified period.

7. The naming of new representatives and the initial meetings we have held with them demonstrate some progress. We expect more to follow. As noted in the opening paragraph, we will report again to the governments in January, and as necessary thereafter.

Signed: Tauno Nieminen John de Chastelain Andrew D. Sens

Belfast, 10 December 1999

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Report of the Independent International Commission on Decommissioning (IICD), 15 November 1999

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REPORT BY THE INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING (IICD) 15 November 1999

Assessment

Ref: Mitchell to de Chastelain; Letter of 2 November 1999

Senator Mitchell's review is focussed on the implementation of the Good Friday Agreement on the basis of the three principles agreed on 25 June:

- An inclusive Executive exercising devolved powers;
- Decommissioning of all paramilitary arms by May 2000;
- Decommissioning to be carried out in a manner determined by the Independent International Commission on Decommissioning [IICD].

Two of the three principles refer to decommissioning and one refers specifically to the Commission. Senator Mitchell has therefore requested an assessment by the Commission to help him in concluding the Review.

The Commission is determined to complete the task set out for us in the Agreement and to complete it within the two-year period which commenced on the endorsement of the Agreement in referendums, North and South.

This is our assessment as to how we can best achieve that, and in particular how principles 2 and 3 can be achieved in this context. Less than seven months now remain in the time-scale set out in the Good Friday Agreement.

While there are difficulties and challenges posed by those paramilitary groups which are not observing a cease-fire, the contribution of those on cease-fire over what is now a protracted period is itself significant.

The Commission has become convinced that a successful outcome to the Review, including the establishment of the political institutions provided for in the Good Friday Agreement, will mark a major move forward in the implementation of the overall settlement envisaged in that Agreement. The implementation of the Agreement in all its aspects will create a new context in which the situation will be transformed.

We remind all the pro-Agreement parties that they are committed:

"... to work constructively and in good faith with the Independent Commission and to use any influence they may have, to achieve the decommissioning of all paramilitary arms within two years following endorsement in referendums North and South of the Agreement and in the context of the implementation of the overall settlement."

And that they have reaffirmed:

"... our total and absolute commitment to exclusively democratic and peaceful means of resolving differences on political issues, and our opposition to any use or threat of force by others for any political purpose, whether in regard to this agreement or otherwise."

The time is now very short to achieve decommissioning within the time-scale intended by the Agreement. Bearing in mind the practical arrangements the Commission will need to make, urgent progress is now needed. Having made all possible preparations, including numerous meetings with the parties and others, we will now play a more active role.

We have previously said we believe that decommissioning is a voluntary act and cannot be imposed. To bring decommissioning about, the Commission will need the co-operation and support of the political parties, using all the influence they have, together with the wholehearted commitment of paramilitary organisations.

While decommissioning is an essential element of the Agreement, our discussions over the past year and a half convince us that the context in which it can be achieved is the overall implementation of that Agreement. All participants have a collective responsibility in this regard.

The process of decommissioning involves a number of steps. To achieve our objective it is now urgent that the appointment by paramilitary organisations of authorised representatives and the holding of discussions about modalities with the Commission take place. Such appointments would represent a significant confidence building measure and would demonstrate each organisation's desire to make a further contribution to the process.

We call on the paramilitary organisations to respond positively by appointing authorised representatives, following which we would set a date for a first meeting with each of them as soon as possible after their appointment. We would issue a report within days of those meetings.

Signed: Tauno Nieminen John de Chastelain Andrew D. Sens

Belfast, 15 November 1999

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REPORT OF THE INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING (IICD)
 2 July 1999

To: The Rt. Hon. Dr. Marjorie Mowlam, MP Secretary of State for Northern Ireland, Belfast	To: Mr. John O'Donoghue, TD, Minister of Justice, Equality and Law Reform, Dublin Belfast
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1. The initial request for this report came from the two Governments, pursuant to the provisions of the Good Friday Agreement. The Commission was asked specifically to comment on progress achieved to date and on prospects for future decommissioning. On 29 June the Commission was prepared to deliver its report to the British and Irish Governments, but the Prime Minister and the Taoiseach requested that delivery be deferred, in the belief that there would be developments having direct relevance to this report. This has proved to be the case, and our report has been restructured as necessary to take account of recent developments.

2. The report provides the Commission's assessment of the current situation regarding decommissioning and the results of discussions held with the parties through 1 July. Since the Governments may choose to distribute the report more widely, and because the Commission has pledged that private discussions will remain confidential, the Commission has been reticent about linking statements or actions directly with named groups or individuals unless these are already in the public domain or are essential to the integrity and purpose of this report.

3. Since its inception in September 1997, the Commission has sought to put in place the measures necessary to facilitate the decommissioning of paramilitary arms and then to execute that task. An Annex to this report summarises the mandate of the Commission, legislation governing its role, and actions taken to carry out its task.

Efforts to Bring About Progress

4. The Decommissioning Acts passed in both jurisdictions in 1997 specified that the decommissioning of paramilitary arms by the Commission required the destruction of those arms.

Working with parties that have actual or alleged links with paramilitary groups, the Commission assessed that two decommissioning methods would be acceptable to the paramilitary groups and the two Governments. These were information leading to the discovery of arms and destruction of arms by the paramilitary group concerned, with verification provided by the Commission. The two methods were confirmed in a Scheme and Regulations issued by the Governments in June 1998. The work of the Commission since then has been to put these methods into effect.

5. In response to a request by the Commission to have points of contact nominated by paramilitary groups, the Ulster Volunteer Force (UVF) nominated Mr. Billy Hutchinson of the Progressive Unionist Party (PUP) in October 1997, and the Loyalist Volunteer Force (LVF) nominated Pastor Kenny McClinton in June 1998. Pastor McClinton resigned from that function in June 1999.

The Commission continues to work with Mr. Gary McMichael, the leader of the Ulster Democratic Party (UDP), to elicit the views of the Ulster Defence Association (UDA). In September 1998, Sinn Fein nominated Mr. Martin McGuinness as that party's representative to the Commission.

6. The UDA and the Irish Republican Army (IRA) had not nominated points of contact with the Commission as of the writing of this report. Furthermore, the Commission has not yet had any contact with acknowledged representatives of the IRA, the Irish National Liberation Army (INLA), the Real Irish Republican Army (RIRA) or the UDA.

7. Since the approval of the Good Friday Agreement, the Commission has worked with party representatives and other points of contact to facilitate the decommissioning of paramilitary arms. Frank discussions have taken place on numerous occasions during that period and useful answers to technical questions about decommissioning have been elicited. As of 1 July 1999, only one decommissioning event had taken place (carried out on 18 December 1998 by the LVF).

8. The Commission has also held numerous meetings with the full range of political parties in Northern Ireland to elicit their advice on how best to carry out its mandate. These meetings have been informative and instructive. Citing the continuing cease-fires, creation of the Assembly, agreement on the structure of a new Northern Ireland government and the commencement of direct dialogue between unionists and republicans, several parties have urged the Commission to determine that progress is being made in the broader political context. That, however, is not in the Commission's remit.

9. All parties to the Good Friday Agreement undertook to work "constructively and in good faith with the Independent Commission, and to use any influence they may have to achieve the decommissioning of all paramilitary arms within two years following endorsement in referendums North and South of the agreement, and in the context of the overall settlement." The parties have assured the Commission they believe they are in compliance with this requirement, and the Commission has no basis for challenging these assertions.

10. During this period, public statements have been made by paramilitary groups regarding their intentions on decommissioning. The IRA said it would not decommission its arms, and loyalist groups said they would not do so until they were clear about the IRA's intentions. During the past ten months the Commission put forward numerous ideas on how to break the impasse over decommissioning. Acting within its mandate to facilitate and encourage decommissioning, the Commission made detailed, specific, and clear suggestions to several parties. The Commission urged that paramilitary groups implement confidence-building measures which would demonstrate a willingness to engage positively with the political process and to allow that process to move forward. No proposal to start actual decommissioning has been accepted by any paramilitary group except the LVF. However, the Sinn Fein statement of 1 July offers promise that decommissioning by all paramilitary groups may now begin. The Commission expects that Sinn Fein's proposal will be endorsed by the IRA and reciprocated by loyalist and other republican paramilitary groups.

Meetings with the Parties - June 1999

11. Between 21 and 28 June the Commission met with ten political parties to confirm their views on the decommissioning process as well as to seek answers to three questions concerning that process. The questions were aimed at focusing attention on areas where the Commission wished to get a stated confirmation of the parties' and the paramilitary groups' intentions. The questions were:

1. Does your party agree that decommissioning of all paramilitary arms should take place by 22 May 2000 as set forth in the Good Friday Agreement, and in the context of the implementation of the overall Agreement? 2. Are there any areas of implementation of the overall Agreement which would demonstrably facilitate the decommissioning process? 3. The Commission is aware of a number of public statements by paramilitary groups since 10 April 1998 regarding decommissioning. Can your party assist the Commission in determining the willingness of paramilitary groups to decommission their weapons by 22 May 2000? If so: a. Is the paramilitary group willing to give the Commission a firm basis for expecting that decommissioning will take place within the timescale set forth in the Good Friday Agreement? And b. While we believe we have general agreement on schemes to be used for decommissioning, when can we expect to receive -- or else conduct negotiations to define -- confirmation of the practical modalities (e.g., types of weapons, and in what order, location of decommissioning events, general time parameters)?

12. On Question (1) the responses were generally supportive of the goal of decommissioning but varied significantly in their emphasis. Some parties argued strongly for immediate and unconditional decommissioning, while others made clear they adhered strictly to the wording of the Good Friday Agreement, or spoke more broadly of their support for decommissioning in the context of the demilitarisation of Northern Ireland. No party suggested that decommissioning ought not to happen by 22 May 2000.

13. On Question (2), the responses were even more varied but included few new proposals. Most parties argued the need for full implementation of the Good Friday Agreement. Two parties felt the question encouraged procrastination.

14. Question (3) received a narrow range of responses. By far the majority of parties told the Commission they could not assist on this question as they had neither weapons nor access to those who did. The Commission was particularly interested in the responses from parties with actual or alleged links to paramilitary groups. It was hoped the question would elicit positive signals from the paramilitary groups themselves. There were no responses to Questions (3)(a) or (3)(b) from either the IRA or the UDA by the 28 June deadline. The UVF provided a response which emphasized the need for the Good Friday Agreement to be implemented in full and an acceptance by republicans that the Agreement is "the final settlement of the constitutional conflict."

Assessing Recent Developments

15. On 1 July, Sinn Fein published a proposal in which they said the following:

"... we believe that all of us, as participants acting in good faith, could succeed in persuading those with arms to decommission them in accordance with the Agreement. We agree that this should be in the manner set down by the Independent Commission on Decommissioning within the terms of the Good Friday Agreement ..."

16. In anticipation that this proposal may translate into a commitment to decommission paramilitary arms, the Commission believes that to complete its mandate by 22 May 2000, the process of decommissioning should begin as soon as possible.

17. The Decommissioning Scheme and Regulations approved by the two governments provide that the process of decommissioning is deemed to have commenced when the Commission is satisfied it has received notice of an intention to decommission arms on behalf of a paramilitary organisation, and that such notice contains sufficient information to contact with the Commission and to decommission specified arms. The Commission will be guided by these provisions. It is the Commission's considered view that the "process of decommissioning" begins in connection with a paramilitary group when it (a) gives an unambiguous commitment that decommissioning will be completed by 22 May 2000, and (b) commences detailed discussions of actual modalities (amounts, types, location, timing) with the Commission through an authorised representative.

18. Once decommissioning commences as set forth above, the Commission expects corresponding moves from all republican and loyalist paramilitary groups.

19. In accordance with the Scheme and Regulations, the Commission foresees the process of decommissioning following a reasonably predictable agenda. We therefore envision the following steps:

- (1) The designation of a point of contact who can speak authoritatively for the paramilitary group;
- (2) Discussions with the designated point of contact regarding:
 - a. The scheme to be used (i.e., self destruction with Commission verification, or information leading to the discovery of arms by the Commission); b. Modalities (i.e., types and amounts of arms, location of the decommissioning event, timing, etc.);
- (3) Agreement to proceed with a specific event or events;
- (4) Execution of the decommissioning event(s);
- (5) Destruction of any residue; and
- (6) Reporting to the Governments.

20. The developments of 1 July give the basis for believing that decommissioning can be completed in the time prescribed by the Good Friday Agreement. There is still sufficient time to do that, but there is a need to get started soon. The Commission is ready and willing to start. It has emphasised its intention to conduct decommissioning in a way that is honourable, safe, verifiable, complete and free from the fear of prosecution.

21. While the Commission is prepared to define a detailed timetable for decommissioning of arms by the main paramilitary groups, it believes this will best be achieved in discussions with the groups, various points of contact. Once such a timetable has been worked out, paramilitary groups will be expected to adhere to it to ensure completion by 22 May 2000, and the Commission will report on progress to the two Governments. The Commission believes that the detailed modalities, the timetable, and the commencement of actual decommissioning should be agreed with the paramilitary groups as soon as possible. The Commission reaffirms the following: Once a contact person has been named, the modalities for decommissioning can be worked out very quickly. Once there is agreement on the modalities, the actual decommissioning can be carried out without delay.

Tauno Nieminen John de Chastelain Donald C. Johnson

Belfast, 2 July 1999

Annex: Commission's Mandate and Actions

ANNEX

REPORT OF THE INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING

COMMISSION'S MANDATE AND ACTIONS

Legislation and Mandate

1. The Agreement to establish the Commission was made between the Government of the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland and the Government of Ireland on 26 August 1997. The Agreement tasked the Commission with the following mandate:

a. To consult with the participants in political negotiations in Northern Ireland, including both Governments, and others whom it deems relevant on the type of scheme or schemes for decommissioning including the role it might play in respect of each scheme; b. To present to the two Governments the proposals for schemes for decommissioning having due regard to the views expressed by those it has consulted; c. To undertake, in accordance with any regulations or arrangements made under the Decommissioning Act, 1997 and any decommissioning schemes within the meaning of section 1, and in accordance with section 3, of the Northern Ireland Arms Decommissioning Act 1997, such tasks that may be required of it to facilitate the decommissioning of arms, including observing, monitoring and verifying decommissioning and receiving and auditing arms; and d. To report periodically to both Governments and, through whatever mechanism they may establish for that purpose, the other participants in political negotiations in Northern Ireland.

2. Legislation enacting terms of the Agreement is found in the two Acts referred to in paragraph 1.c. above - The Northern Ireland Decommissioning Act 1997 (UK) and The Decommissioning Act 1997 (Ireland) - and the attention of the Commission was drawn to the Report of the International Body of 22 January 1996.

3. In both Acts it was specified that methods and manners (schemes) to be used for decommissioning require the destruction of the arms being decommissioned.

4. On 24 September the two Governments jointly appointed three Commissioners from Canada, Finland and the United States of America as members of the Commission, one of whom was designated as Chairman.

Resources

5. The Commission comprises the three Commissioners and three assistants drawn from the same three countries. Four secretaries, also drawn from Canada, Finland and the United States, are divided between the Commission's offices in each of Belfast and Dublin. At the request of the two Governments, the Canadian Armed Forces and the U.S. Army have made available to the Commission, on an as-required basis, two officers who are experts on arms, ammunition and explosives ordnance disposal. These officers have taken part in refresher training with the defence forces in both jurisdictions, and they are called to join the Commission when needed.

6. The moneys, premises, facilities and services necessary for the proper functioning of the Commission have been provided by the two Governments in accordance with the legislation and on a basis determined by the Governments.

Consultations in 1997

7. The role of the Commission is to facilitate the voluntary decommissioning of firearms, ammunition, explosives and explosive substances (hereinafter referred to as "arms"), held by paramilitary groups. At the outset, the Commission consulted with participants in the talks process, and with the security forces in both jurisdictions, to clarify issues relating to the possible implementation of the decommissioning methods identified by the International Body. The purpose was to see which of these, if any, might be acceptable to paramilitary groups on ceasefire, once the decommissioning process had begun.

8. On 21 November 1997 the Commission submitted an Initial Report to the Liaison Sub-Committee on Decommissioning. This report addressed key issues related to the first two tasks of the Commission's mandate and outlined a basic scenario for decommissioning.

9. After further consultation, the Commission concentrated on developing a decommissioning scheme which included two possible methods:

a. Arms collected by the Commission, or by the designated representatives of either Government, as the result of information provided by paramilitary groups; and b. Arms destroyed by paramilitary groups themselves with verification by the Commission.

10. Practical arrangements in relation to decommissioning were to be set out in a scheme and in regulations to be made by the Secretary of State for Northern Ireland and the Minister for Justice, Equality and Law Reform, in accordance with legislation passed earlier in the year. Based on this requirement the Commission drafted a proposal for a decommissioning scheme including the two aforementioned methods, which it believed would represent a workable basis for achieving the decommissioning of paramilitary arms. The proposal was submitted to the Talks participants on 15 December 1997 for their consideration.

The Mechanics of Decommissioning

11. In a meeting on 14 January 1998, the Liaison Sub-Committee on Decommissioning discussed the Commission's proposals for methods of decommissioning. The following day the Commission formally submitted its recommendations for a decommissioning scheme to the two Governments, completing the first and second tasks of its mandate. On 25 February both Governments presented to the Liaison Sub-Committee on Decommissioning their proposals on how they intended to give effect to the Commission's recommendations.

12. During the spring of 1998, to get acquainted with all aspects of their mandate, the Commissioners and assistants travelled frequently in both jurisdictions and consulted experts on forensic science, ammunition and explosives, destruction techniques and disposal of residue. The acquisition of commercial sources for vehicles and equipment was also explored.

13. Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) were developed to guide the conduct of the Commission's involvement in decommissioning events. It is anticipated that specific arrangements and measures during each individual decommissioning event will vary, depending on the method used and the nature of the operational circumstances existing at the time.

14. Operations Centers, to be activated during decommissioning events, were established in Belfast and Dublin.

15. The possibility remains that State agencies in either jurisdiction will be involved in the conduct of decommissioning operations, either acting as representatives of the Government ("designated representatives"), or as agents of the Commission in accordance with the agreed method used. To that end the Commission established permanent liaison with the Royal Ulster Constabulary, the Garda Síochána, the British Army and the Irish Defence Forces.

The Good Friday Agreement

16. The Good Friday Agreement of 10 April 1998 was the culmination of a process of negotiation that began on 10 June 1996 in Belfast. Parties to the Agreement confirmed their intention to work constructively and in good faith with the Commission, and to use any influence they may have, to achieve the decommissioning of all paramilitary arms within two years following the referendums held on 22 May 1998 and in the context of the implementation of the overall settlement.

17. Both Governments committed to take the necessary steps to facilitate the decommissioning process, to include bringing the relevant scheme or regulations into force by the end of June 1998. A decommissioning scheme in Northern Ireland and Regulations in Ireland came into effect on 30 June 1998. They provide a workable basis for achieving the decommissioning of paramilitary arms.

Contact Persons

18. The Commission is tasked to facilitate the decommissioning of arms held by paramilitary groups. To assist in that task the Commission asked that paramilitary groups nominate a representative or point of contact with the Commission through whom it could communicate.

19. In October 1997 the Ulster Volunteer Force (UVF) and Red Hand Commando (RHQ) nominated Mr. Billy Hutchinson from the Progressive Unionist Party (PUP) to be their point of contact with the Commission. In June 1998 the Loyalist Volunteer Force (LVF) nominated Pastor Kenny McClinton as their point of contact, though in June 1999 he resigned from this post. In September 1998 Sinn Fein nominated Mr. Martin McGuinness as the party's point of contact with the Commission. While the UVF and LVF have not named a point of contact, the leader of the Ulster Democratic Party (UDP), Mr. Gary McMichael, and his colleagues, have met several times with the Commission. All of these individuals have been helpful in providing the Commission with a better understanding of attitudes within the wider loyalist and republican communities regarding decommissioning.

Decommissioning

20. Contact with the UVF through their intermediary led to a decommissioning event on 18 December 1998. That paramilitary group decommissioned four sub-machine guns, two rifles, two pistols, a sawn-off shotgun, 348 rounds of ball ammunition, 31 shotgun shells, five electrical detonators, two pipe bombs, two weapons stocks and five assorted magazines. The items described were destroyed in accordance with Commission procedures the day they were received and the residue was disposed of the same day also. At the UVFs request the event was covered by the media. A report on this event was provided to both governments in accordance with the Commission's SOP.

Public Profile

21. With the exception of the press conference on 18 December 1998 to answer media queries about the LVF decommissioning, and the intervention made following the Prime Minister's announcement of the Hillsborough Declaration on 1 April 1999, the Commission has had no public statements since September 1998. The Commission has taken this course of action in the belief that avoiding publicity would give the Commission a greater chance to work with paramilitary groups or their representatives, to win their confidence, and to advance the prospects for decommissioning.

22. The Commission's silence should not be interpreted as inactivity. Over the course of the last ten months the Commission has had numerous meetings with political parties in Northern Ireland, with the two governments, with the security forces in both jurisdictions, with the churches, and with local special interest organisations.

Reporting

23. Throughout this process, the Commission has kept both governments informed in detail about its efforts and its assessment of prospects for success. A number of these meetings have taken place at the highest governmental level. The two governments have likewise shared with the Commission their views on their own efforts, and this has been helpful to the Commission.

Signed: Tauno Nieminen John de Chastelain Andrew D. Senn

Belfast, 2 July 1999

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